

CoSeC 2025 Year-end Forum Report

Durham University
5th November 2025

M Hoang (editor)

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**Computational Science Centre
for Research Communities**

Community Forum

Wednesday 5 November 2025

Durham University

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Foreword

The UK High Performance Computing community is widely admired internationally for its high degree of coordination and resulting impact. Collaborative Computational Projects have existed for more than 40 years, complemented more recently by High End Computing Consortia and other Network activities. Such successful open collaboration remains essential to maintain, further strengthen and build on UK leadership at the cutting edge of current HPC research - particularly when developments are moving at pace in AI and Quantum Computing as well as established digital simulation.

For many years the CCPs were coordinated by a Steering Panel of HPC community leaders and research council representatives, which has now expanded into a wider Forum embracing all UK existing and new HPC communities to ensure most effective sharing of information, skills and insights amongst these and right across UKRI. This latest Forum Report attempts to capture key emerging points in a succinct fashion to inform a wider audience so that the collective impact of contributions from the gathered experts and input from CoSeC can be maximised.

The Durham Forum allowed community chairs to receive latest information directly from all UKRI Research Council representatives, DRI, SSI and CoSeC, while directly feeding back, as well as discussing the developing Forum format and community aspirations and priorities for effective future funding given the new compute resource support landscape.

The Forum applauded the large investments in National HPC and AI compute resources, together with announced complementary distributed National Compute Resources, which provide capabilities needed for them to target identified opportunities, and received assurances that further essential community recurrent funding was planned to address the current shortfall beyond 2026.

Prof. Mark Savill, Chair of CoSeC Community Forum

Introduction

The CoSeC Community Forum is a bi-annual meeting involving the communities directly involved with the CoSeC programme, including the [Collaborative Computational Projects \(CCPs\)](#), the [High-End Computing Consortia \(HECs\)](#) plus representation from across the [UKRI research councils](#).

The Forum is an opportunity for the [communities](#) to come together to report on recent activities and future opportunities as well as to discuss national strategy related to computational research. The meeting provides networking possibilities and discussion activities that help to share information and best practice between the communities as well as identify potential for future cross-community projects.

This meeting was hosted by the Chair of [CCP-AHC](#), Dr Eamonn Bell, at the University of Durham and had an agenda designed to explore some wide-reaching DRI topics particularly relevant for communities such as identifying impact and related metrics beyond traditional research outputs and inclusivity as a driver for better research communities. Alongside these important topics, the future of the UKRI research community model was a key topic, with this meeting timed at the point just ahead of the next phases for both the CCPs and HECs.

Agenda

Welcome	Mark Savill (Cranfield University)	10:00
Minutes (June 2025) and matters arising	Mark Savill (Cranfield University)	10:10
1. CoSeC Update 2. CoSeC Grand Challenges	1. Stephen Longshaw (UKRI-STFC) 2. Alison Oliver (UKRI-STFC)	10:30
Break		11:30
UKRI DRI Update	Barbara Montanari (UKRI-STFC)	11:45
UKRI Council DRI Session	UKRI Council Representatives	12:00
Lunch and Poster Session		13:00
The Hidden Ref	Simon Hettrick (Software Sustainability Institute)	14:00
CoSeC – CAKE EDI Working Group	Eleanor Broadway (EPCC, Edinburgh)	14:30
Break		15:00
Introduction to the Forum Discussion	Damian Jones (UKRI-STFC)	15:15
Forum Discussion: 1. Thoughts about the future format of the forum. 2. Community aspirations.	ALL - See attached guidance notes for further information We will allow 20mins discussion per topic followed by 10mins per group for feedback presentations	15:30
Any other business, wrap up and meeting close	Mark Savill (Cranfield University)	16:50

Summary

The Community Forum, hosted at Durham University in November, brought together representatives from the Collaborative Computational Projects (CCPs), High-End Computing consortia (HECs) and UKRI councils to discuss developments in the UK's computational research landscape. The meeting focused on major infrastructure investments, community-led initiatives and opportunities for collaboration, alongside honest discussions about supporting research communities during a time of funding uncertainty.

Key Updates:

The Forum reaffirmed **CoSeC**'s essential role in connecting grassroots research communities with UKRI's strategic, top-down programmes. Updates covered the 2024–2027 programme, including external community funding, collaboration opportunities and cross-cutting projects that benefit multiple CCPs and consortia.

The CoSeC Fellows cohort continues to grow, with ten new fellows joining this year. The cohort spans diverse research areas with improved gender balance.

CoSeC's **Grand Challenges** initiative led by Alison Oliver (Research Community Manager), has moved from concept to near-final outputs. Communities have worked together to identify shared priorities and challenges, which are now being shaped into accessible statements explaining each community's aims, rationale and alignment with wider national priorities. When published, these Grand Challenges will give stakeholders in UKRI, government and industry a clear narrative, helping communities articulate their collective needs and make the case for funding that delivers impact.

The **DRI** programme's direction for research infrastructure is now clearer. Achievements include the fully operational Isambard AI service supporting projects across the UK, approved business cases for next-generation supercomputing and AI facilities, and ongoing work on federated access models.

On the EPSRC side, support for Tier 2 facilities will end in March 2026, with ARCHER2 extended to November 2026 and a new national supercomputing service expected to launch in 2027. Across UKRI, councils reported further investment in digital and data infrastructure, such as AHRC's long-term DiSSCo UK digitisation programme, a £155.6 million, 10-year investment in digitising UK national science collections and NERC's £12.5 million AI for Environmental Science call, alongside other AI, software and infrastructure initiatives.

The CCP/consortia model continues to be seen as a success, with growing interest in "Community Centres of Excellence" to embed expertise, software development, training and knowledge sharing around access to national compute. There is active work from the DRI side to ensure community voices are reflected in infrastructure planning through routes like ASCEND.

An important topic at the Forum was research culture and how contributions are recognised. We were pleased to welcome Professor Simon Hettrick from the Software Sustainability Institute and Chair of the **Hidden REF** campaign, who spoke about the Hidden REF campaign's work to recognise diverse research outputs, including software development and other non-traditional contributions that are often overlooked. With five years of Research England funding secured, the campaign can continue to influence policy and practice around valuing all types of research contribution, particularly in areas relevant to the CoSeC community.

Alongside this, the **CAKE–CoSeC EDI Working Group** is now active and working to turn high-level EDI policy into practical change. Priorities include improving recruitment practices, fostering a sense of belonging, and building better structures to attract and retain a more diverse range of technical and research software workforce.

Forum Discussion

A key part of the forum was open discussion. Members split into four breakout groups, including one online room, to explore how both the Forum and CoSeC should evolve. Topics included the future format of the Forum, community aspirations and funding priorities. The breakout format allowed for more honest, detailed conversations with key insights shared with the full group.

A recurring concern was the looming “funding cliff” in late 2026. Participants stressed the need for a clear transition plan before changing the Forum's format. Members also emphasised the need for reliable, long-term and flexible funding to support planning.

There was strong support for a two-day, in-person Forum, with a shorter online meeting later in the year. There was also interest in co-locating with other relevant events like Durham HPC Days, RSECon or the CoSeC Conference to build connections across communities and avoid clashes with already busy calendars.

Across the board, there was a clear appetite for more knowledge sharing through lightning talks, community-led presentations and informal discussion while maintaining space for relationship building with research councils and UKRI.

Communities also flagged several ongoing priorities:

- Flexible funding to balance networking, staffing and strategic activities.
- Better coordination between distributed (university-based) and centralised (national) resources.
- Support for newer communities adopting large-scale compute and diverse platforms.
- Improved data infrastructure and management practices.
- Continued investment in training and hands-on help.
- Closer industry partnerships and exploring vertical integration such as linking DiRAC and CCP services.

Conclusions and Next Steps

This meeting was the second iteration of the new Forum format with focus moved away from detailed technical review across all communities to a higher-level strategic and policy driven one. This move was the right one as the scope (e.g. number) of the community landscape has increased such that sensibly reviewing technical details of 25 communities in a single day event is unmanageable, and simultaneously the need to look at the bigger picture of the DRI landscape is pressing.

The key question, therefore, is whether losing a view of the technical outputs across the communities is sufficiently justified by having the time to spend looking at high-level topics. Before starting my CoSeC overview, I hinted that I thought the event had lost something important by steering away from technical details and while each community still submits a detailed technical report that is compiled as part of this document, there is something lost when the Chair of each community is unable to articulate and present this in person. To explore this issue more thoroughly, time was dedicated during the Forum Discussion session to consider the future format of the event with that in mind.

My overview presentation was primarily intended to disseminate information about CoSeC and the wider DRI landscape, however I took the opportunity to launch the new [CoSeC Grand Challenges](#) part of our website where the outputs of work undertaken by the CoSeC Programme Office in collaboration with the Chairs of each community and their CoSeC Project Lead are now available. Each amount to a short document describing the real-world challenges that drive the communities in their research and give purpose and meaning to the software that they maintain, develop and apply. I firmly believe this collection of documents represents a rich resource for UK policymakers to tap into when deciding where the future of research investment lies. Further outputs from this work will follow in Q1 2026.

On the agenda at this Forum meeting were talks from Eleanor Broadway from EPCC and Simon Hettrick from the SSI. These covered some key ongoing activities within the DRI landscape, Eleanor talked about the UKRI DRI funded [Computational Abilities Knowledge Exchange \(CAKE\)](#) project and the recently announced CAKE-CoSeC Working Group around Equality, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI). Simon presented the Research England funded [HiddenREF](#) exercise, which clearly highlighted how aligned the outputs of CCPs and HECs are with target research object types and RTP outputs that the HiddenREF has set out to recognise.

The meeting came at a time where communities are understandably looking to UKRI for news around their next funded opportunity as the known funding for all communities currently comes to an end over the course of Q4 2026. There were presentations from the UKRI DRI programme as well as more specific updates from each of UKRI's councils. The synopsis is that the hardware infrastructure landscape of the DRI will be well known by the end of 2026, with a new machine hosted at EPCC to replace ARCHER2 and multiple smaller machines hosted around the country, effectively replacing the Tier-2 network and collectively now called the National Compute Resources (NCRs).

At the time of writing, it is understood that the right mechanism for coordinating access (and development) for these NCR's is the community model, so the question that now needs answering is what UKRI wants this to look like and what that means in terms of opportunities for

the CCPs and HECs. I am personally hopeful that by the time of the next Community Forum the funding picture will be much clearer with lots more information available.

This neatly leads to a key outcome of this meeting which came through the Forum Discussion session. As mentioned, a question we posed was what the future of these meetings should look like and almost unanimously it was agreed that moving to a single in-person event per year was a sensible approach. This event would be extended over two days, retaining a hybrid format for flexibility of attendance, and would be followed later in the year by a shorter virtual catch-up similar in design to the existing UKRI EPSRC *HEC Director's* meeting.

The proposal for moving to a longer, single meeting was motivated by the idea that the Forum shouldn't have to choose between high-level strategic discussion and more detailed technical knowledge exchange, therefore day one would be like the current event with day two being driven by the Chairs of the communities and facilitated by CoSeC. In the coming months we will work to design this new format and then aim to announce it well in advance, with a view to running it towards the end of Q2 2026, approximately 6-8 months down the line.

I left this meeting in Durham more enthused than ever about the state of the computational community landscape within the UK. Despite the ongoing uncertainty around future direction and funding from within UKRI, communities continue to adapt, grow and thrive. The total number of funded CCPs and HECs that CoSeC works with directly now sits at 25, with further communities out there. Following our recent call to create scoping projects for new CCPs the landscape is becoming truly cross-UKRI in nature and the tangible outputs seen from this model can only be described as world-class.

I have no doubt that what we have now is fundamentally the right approach and it is clear from recent opportunities that it is adaptable to whatever UKRI needs the community approach to be, with this in mind I am very excited to see what next year brings.

Dr Stephen Longshaw, Director of CoSeC

APPENDIX

These reports are reproduced as provided by community Chairs in a template as a response to a request for information from the CoSeC Programme Office.

Collaborative Computational Projects (CCP) Reports

Materials Science

CCP-NC for the Period 01/04/2025 to 30/09/2025

Dr J. Kane Shenton, STFC core support

Prof. Paul Hodgkinson, Chair of CCP-NC Chair

1. Background

Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) is a useful technique to determine chemical structure, especially in compounds of which it is hard to produce single crystals big enough for diffraction techniques, as commonly found in organic molecules. NMR Crystallography is the technique of using quantum-mechanical simulations to predict NMR spectra to a high degree of precision and combining this with experiment to open new ways of exploring structure in not yet understood crystals, such as new pharmaceuticals. CCP-NC has the objective of disseminating and promoting this approach throughout the experimental NMR community in the UK and worldwide.

2. Highlights for the current reporting period

In May 2025 we organised a 50-person, two-day workshop in Manchester bringing together some of the grand challenges in NMR crystallography with potential solutions in the form of machine learning (ML) capabilities. The meeting focussed on discussions between these two communities, with questions around the general model of interaction (e.g. collaboration vs training) as well as how to tackle particular scientific challenges together. The feedback collected after the workshop was positive, with many respondents appreciating the productive engagement between the two communities. The discussions also helped to shape the CCP-NC ML projects. The event was co-organised by Kane Shenton (CoSeC project lead for CCP-NC) and Albert Bartók-Partay (University of Warwick), with extremely valuable support from the CoSeC events team.

We have released the first version of our schema package for computational solid-state NMR data ([link](#)), collaborating closely with PSDI, Exact Lab, Nomad and the developers of the CASTEP and Quantum Espresso density functional theory (DFT) codes. This schema lays the groundwork for making the field more FAIR-compliant, as well as setting and documenting common standards for NMR-related tensor data. Tied to the schema package, we have also been developing the Nomad Magres parser, allowing users to deposit such NMR data into the Nomad database in the (CCP-NC-developed) standard file format.

We have been working on getting our Soprano python library “AI-ready” by introducing support for standard ML-related file formats and pipelines. This also includes developing the features for correctly averaging derived tensor quantities over sets of structures, from e.g. molecular dynamics trajectories. These features have been added in releases [v0.10.0](#) and [v0.10.1](#) of Soprano. To further the interoperability of our approach, we have refactored the way we generate nuclear spin systems based on the outputs of DFT calculations. The new approach allows for better interoperability with spin simulation programs, such as MRSimulator and Simpson.

Finally, we held the first CCP-NC Townhall meeting, organised by the Community Development Group (CDG) in June 2025. We outlined the current work done by the CCP-NC, as well as our future plans and a request for input into the CCP-NC roadmap development. The CDG received three very strong applications for the early-career representative. After reviewing the applications, it was decided that all three applicants should be invited to form an early-career sub-group of the CDG with one member being elected to attend CDG meetings to report discussions and ideas from the early career perspective, and who will also represent CCP-NC at the CoSeC CAKE EDI working group meetings.

3. Overview of work relating to accelerated computing

CASTEP's NMR functionality is the key software for our user community, since it allows experimental NMR parameters for a given crystal structure to be calculated from first principles using Density Functional Theory (DFT). Although some other DFT codes, notably Quantum Espresso and VASP, now also have this functionality, CASTEP remains the most well-developed and dominates use in the UK. Hence it is critical for the NMR crystallography community that CASTEP, and CASTEP-NMR in particular, can work effectively with the latest hardware, especially GPU acceleration.

Work has begun on our plan to port CASTEP's NMR functionality to run on GPUs using specialist RSE support. The initial steps involved profiling and benchmarking the existing CPU functionality. Here it was found that there were significant efficiency gains to be made. The existing GPU port of CASTEP has been done using the OpenACC framework, however work is currently being done to move the port to the more vendor-agnostic OpenMP standard.

For the relatively small suite of benchmarks tested, the OpenACC GPU port has shown significant performance improvement over the existing CASTEP-NMR code with very little optimisation, in some case offering a 10x speed up. As the OpenMP GPU port continues, it should quickly become as efficient as the OpenACC code. Once this is achieved, work can continue to optimise the NMR calculations specifically. This should reduce the "time to science" and improve the energy efficiency of CASTEP-NMR calculations, which will reduce the carbon footprint of NMR research.

GPU acceleration for CASTEP-NMR will be developed in the wider context of support for heterogeneous computing: adapting codes and runtime systems to exploit diverse computing environments; and training users who will not be experts in heterogeneous computing. Without support, there is the risk that users will run demanding

calculations very inefficiently. The GPU port will be extensively tested, along with appropriate documentation on how to get the most out of the available hardware.

4. Current plans, developments, or specific applications of AI

In addition to the workshop organised in May, the CCP-NC has two major workplan strands to our AI strategy:

- i. Facilitate and demonstrate the use of machine-learned interatomic potentials (MLIPs) to accelerate computationally intensive DFT calculations. These help to bridge the gap between DFT's feasible length- and timescales and real-world problems. We have completed two case-studies on the use of MLIPs so far. The first looked at the length- and time-scale limits of the MACE family of potentials in describing the dynamics of amorphous drug compounds. The second was around building a pipeline for predicting average observable quantities in aluminosilicate zeolite materials. The outcome of this second project is lightweight software package that leverages “foundational MLIPs” to generate ensembles of low-energy structures through a basin-hopping approach. The code and ensembles generated will be shared with our industrial collaborators in Johnson-Matthey.
- ii. Prediction of NMR observables via custom ML models, circumventing the need for expensive DFT calculations. [ShiftML's](#) successful prediction of chemical shifts has already gained traction among non-computational researchers, and rapid advances are expected. However, constructing suitable training databases for ML—structurally diverse, but representative of target systems—requires significant expertise. We have been developing a software pipeline, built upon widely used existing frameworks (MACE and GraphPES) to allow users to easily train a ML model for predicting full magnetic shielding tensors based on on-the-fly run (or pre-computed) DFT NMR data. The software also allows users to easily use previously trained models to make predictions on new structures.

5. Up to 5 research outputs that create an impact story for your community from the reporting period

The CCP-NC is advancing data-driven approaches to computational NMR crystallography. Our efforts focus both on the standardisation and curation of computational NMR data—exemplified by the release of the NMR Schema package ([v0.1.0](#))—and on the development of pipelines for processing such data, as demonstrated by Soprano [v0.10.1](#).

In parallel, we are exploring the application of machine learning (ML) in NMR crystallography through a collaborative project with Johnson Matthey. This work involves (1) developing computationally efficient methods to explore the vast landscape of possible zeolite structures using pre-trained ML interatomic potentials, and (2) establishing a framework for training and fine-tuning ML models to predict NMR tensors effectively. Together, these efforts aid in the reduction of the overall

computational carbon footprint by minimising reliance on expensive density functional theory calculations.

6. Workshops and new opportunities*

Date	Title	Description
8-12 Dec. 2025	CASTEP Workshop	Annual CASTEP workshop at Oxford University (around 40 participants).
TBC	CCP-NC Online	Our online lunchtime discussion seminar series. We have two planned: one focussing on how to run CASTEP GIPAW calculations efficiently on HPC systems and one on our post-processing python library: Soprano

7. Issues and problems*

There has been some impact of the continued restrictions on core staff support, but we have responded creatively to the evolving circumstances and have continued to make steady progress on all our key objectives.

CCP5 for the Period 01/04/2025 to 30/09/2025

Prof. Paola Carbone, Chair of CCP5

Dr Alin-Marin Elena, CoSeC Project Lead

1. Background

CCP5 is the Collaborative Computational Project for computer simulation of condensed phase materials at length scales spanning from atomistic to mesoscopic levels. Founded more than 40 years ago, CCP5 has promoted the involvement of UK scientists in collaborative research achieved via software and methodology development, training, networking and outreach. It provides support for all UK scientists engaged in developing, applying and exploiting computer simulation methods for condensed matter systems. CCP5 has over 1500 UK and international members, which comprise research active academic faculty staff in 35 different UK universities and at least 18 other UK industrial, charitable or government organisations. A distinctive feature of CCP5 is its successful strategy of developing and disseminating new codes and methods for all kinds of materials problems. These include solid-state materials, polymers, colloidal solutions, liquids and mixtures, liquid crystals, surfaces and interfaces, homogeneous and heterogeneous catalysts, mineral, bio-mineral, organic and bio-molecular systems.

2. Highlights for the current reporting period

CCP5 Summer School 2025: The **CCP5 Summer School 2025** was an intensive training program focused on **molecular and materials simulation**, specifically designed for newcomers to the field, such as PhD students. The school, organised by CCP5 and sponsored by CECAM with support in teaching from CCP9, MCC, UKCOMES and CCP

BioSim for advanced courses, took place from **July 20th to 31st, 2025**, at **Newcastle University**. The program was structured in three main parts to provide a comprehensive and progressive learning experience. It began with a two-day **programming course**, where participants could opt for either **Python** or **modern Fortran** to build a necessary computational foundation. This was followed by the core of the school, consisting of five days dedicated to the **basics of molecular simulation**. These foundational lectures and extensive practical sessions covered critical topics like **Statistical Mechanics, Molecular Dynamics, Monte Carlo Methods**, and different **Free Energy Methods**, aiming to solidify the theoretical background and practical skills in computational chemistry and physics. The final three days were devoted to **advanced courses**, allowing students to specialise in key emerging and established areas of simulation. These options included **Mesoscale Methods, Ab Initio (First-Principles) Simulations, Biomolecular Simulation**, and the application of **Machine Learning for Interatomic Potentials**. Overall, the school's purpose is to provide early-career researchers with the essential skills and insights required to successfully conduct research in molecular, liquid, and solid-state simulations. This year we had 72 students from all Europe, US, Mexico and UK. Split UK international is roughly 50:50. Best oral presentation winner was Akanksha Nawani, Sorbonne University, France and posters winners, Nga Man Cheng, University of Nottingham, UK, Gustave Szczepan, CEA, France, Sarah Haggemueller, Technical University of Munich, Germany, Matthew Ludwig, University of Bristol, UK. More details and pictures on summer2025.ccp5.ac.uk

CaMML - Chemistry and Materials Machine Learning School 2025. This school focuses on the intersection of **Chemistry, Materials Science, and Machine Learning**. It is dedicated to training researchers, at PhD Level, in using machine learning techniques for applications in chemical and materials simulations and research. The event took place from **March 31st to April 4th, 2025**, at the **Daresbury Laboratory**. School had 43 participants from UK and overseas, with a 65% UK and 35% international. Poster winners were Simone Vari, Politecnico di Milano, Italy, Sophie Bennett, University of Southampton, UK, Gustavo Chaparro, Imperial College London, UK. More information and pictures on spring2025.camml.ac.uk School are in collaboration between PSDI/AI HUB Alchemy, CCP5 and CCP9.

The CCP5 Annual General Meeting (AGM) 2025 was held at the University of Liverpool from September 8th to 10th, 2025. This event serves as the primary meeting for CCP5. As an AGM, the meeting typically features a scientific programme with talks from invited speakers, presentations of new research, and discussions on the future direction of the CCP5 community. We had 65 participants from UK and international. Meeting has a strong focus on early career participants. Invited speakers this year ranged from University of Cambridge to Max Planck Institute in Mainz. Full details on agm45.ccp5.ac.uk.

A one-day Machine learning interatomic potentials training was delivered at MCC Conference held at Daresbury Laboratory 7-11 July 2025.

CCP5 Undergraduate Program run again this year, with 5 Bursaries being awarded to University of Durham, UCL, University of Manchester, University of Strathclyde and University of Cardiff.

On the specific work packages: DL_FIELD work package Prepared a full set of 4 DL_FIELD tutorials (available via the DL_FIELD homepage) covering main functionalities of user-interest (applying basic FF, using user-defined FFs, solvating molecules, creating boxes of pure solvent).

Progress has been made towards integrating DL_FIELD into a wider Python wrapper for the automated creation of single polymer chains, FF assignment, polymer box creation and equilibration, and property extraction. Progress includes monomer SMILES to xyz procedure tested, Python wrapper created to allow easy DL_FIELD FF parameter assignment, and random walk box builder code in early stages (has functionality for packing coarse-grained monomer beads at high densities, chemical detail still to be included). 74 atomistic polymers have been tested with an automated set of annealing cycles for equilibration (using DL_FIELD output topology and structures), with structural metrics to test for convergence (RDF, radius of gyration, end to end distance). Finally, we have a procedure to automatically detect monomers in simulation output structures from their SMILES, which is used to automate the extraction of contour length and persistence length.

3. Overview of work relating to accelerated computing

There is no GPU development at the moment, with the work due to start in November 2025. Only incidental GPU work was undertaken in the context of MLIPs. Benchmarking of MACE on multiple GPUs and variety of systems was undertaken. Results show MACE is competitive for system sizes of interest to majority of material scientists: tens of thousands of atoms with speeds of close to 1 ns per day. Work was presented at various workshops and conferences over the summer.

4. Current plans, developments, or specific applications of AI

On the ML work package. The bulk of the work concentrates on porous materials part of the workplan. A specific ML forcefield was released for Metal Organic Frameworks. We are already working on a second generation which is based on better suited quantum mechanics approximations to allow comparison with experiment. In parallel work was undertaken for using MLIPs to simulate zeolites. This proved to be very successful. Both these works resulted in publications, see below. Work on MLIPs for molten salts is also taking place, with an ALC PhD studentship being awarded to continue this work.

5. Up to 5 research outputs that create an impact story for your community from the reporting period

Releases of janus_core, <https://github.com/stfc/janus-core/> this allows easy use of various MLIPs and of the most common foundation models with little effort.

DL_FIELD release

Machine learned potential for high-throughput phonon calculations of metal—organic frameworks: AM Elena, PD Kamath, T JaffreLOT Inizan, AS Rosen, F Zanca, KA Persson, npj Computational Materials 11 (1), 125, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41524-025-01611-8>

Modelling silica using MACE-MP machine learnt interatomic potentials
 JA Nasir, J Guan, W Jee, SM Woodley, AA Sokol, CRA Catlow, A Elena
 Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics 2025, **27**, 19784-19796,
<https://doi.org/10.1039/D5CP01882J>

6. Workshops and new opportunities*

1. CaMML School 31/03-04/04 April 2025 Daresbury Laboratory, spring2025.camml.ac.uk
2. CCP5 Summer School 20-31st July University of Newcastle, summer2025.ccp5.ac.uk
3. AGM 45, University of Liverpool 8-10 September 2025, agm45.ccp5.ac.uk
4. CAMML School 13-17, April 2026 Daresbury Laboratory, spring2026.ccamml.ac.uk
5. CCP5 Summer School 19-30th July University of Newcastle, summer2026.ccp5.ac.uk
6. AGM46, to be decided September 2026, agm46.ccp5.ac.uk

Sponsored community events.

1. Lennard-Jones Centre-CECAM Meeting 2025: From Electrons to Atoms to Molecules and Materials, University of Cambridge, 1-5 September 2025, <https://ljc.group.cam.ac.uk/dft-2025>
2. Non-Equilibrium Molecular Dynamics (NEMD) Meeting, July 2026, London
3. Design of sustainable polymer for barrier and transport applications, University of Strathclyde 2025
4. Thermodynamics 2026, London September 13-15
5. EMLG/JMLG Annual Meeting 2026: Mixing, De-mixing, and Self-Assembly from Solution, University of Strathclyde, August 31- September 4 2026

7. Issues and problems*

None

CCP9 for the Period 1/4/25 to 30/9/2025

Prof. Stewart Clark, Chair of CCP9

1. Background

No changes to previous general background.

The Chair and CCP9 community wish to thank Leon Petit for his role as CCP9 secretary for many years and also welcomes Jerome Jackson as the new CCP9 secretary.

The EPSRC CCP9 grant has a no cost extension to November 2026 (previously due to end November 2025).

2. Highlights for the current reporting period

CCP9 lead the organisation of an important networking and training event in theoretical spectroscopy: the “CECAM/ALC/CCP9 Spectroscopy Masterclass” was held at STFC Rutherford Appleton Laboratory, Didcot, 2-5 September 2025 and brought together experimentalists from the large-scale facilities and theoreticians working in modelling spectroscopy to learn state-of-the-art calculation methods and discuss future challenges and opportunities. The school, which was funded by CECAM and the Ada Lovelace Centre, as well as CCP9, attracted about 60 participants from across Europe and beyond. (More information here <https://ccp9.ac.uk/spectroscopy-masterclass/>)

CCP9 also supported the large conference “Lennard-Jones Centre-CECAM Meeting 2025: From Electrons to Atoms to Molecules and Materials” (<https://ljc.group.cam.ac.uk/dft-2025>) which celebrated the work of Professors Mike Payne, Volker Heine, and Richard Needs, all of whom have been extremely active proponents for CCP9 throughout their distinguished careers.

CCP9 welcomed Professor Mark van Schilfgaard, Chief Theorist at National Renewable Energy Laboratory, USA, as the 2026 CCP9 Visiting Professor (8-12 September 2025). Mark gave invited talks/seminars at the University of St Andrews, London’s Thomas Young Centre, Loughborough University and the University of Warwick as well as speaking at the CECAM/ALC/CCP9 Spectroscopy Masterclass. Mark’s talks were entitled: “Response functions of correlated systems within Green’s function theory” and “Ab initio Green’s function theory of Unconventional Superconductivity”.

CCP9 based efforts in Quantum Computing (QC), led by core-support team member Dr Leon Petit, were focussed on learning the basic tools of QC circuit construction mainly based on IBM's Qiskit programming environment, studying the different ways of porting the ingredients of quantum chemistry to qubits and the various hardware infrastructures being developed for running simulations. Two applications currently under investigation are focussing on how to implement Green’s function on Rydberg atoms (in collaboration with Paolo Trevisanutto within CCP-QC), and a collaboration with colleagues at Open University on developing the theoretical framework for analogue quantum simulators (optical lattice) of realistic materials. Improved checkpointing/restarting capabilities in ONETEP was completed by core support team member Dr Manuel dos Santos Dias at the end of September. The improved checkpointing/restarting consists of a new XML log file that contains the internal state of about 1000 variables that affect the calculations plus a trace of files being written. This can then be used to figure out how to continue or reuse data for a subsequent calculation. This feature is now available in ONETEP.

A new project has been commenced on automatic calculation of crystal field parameters for modelling various spectroscopies and magnetic phenomena for localised d- and f-electrons in solids, connecting DFT codes (e.g., CASTEP) to crystal field solvers such as Quanty. This project is a collaboration between the CCP9 team, led by Dr Jerome Jackson, and the Universities of Manchester, Birmingham and Oxford.

3. Overview of work relating to accelerated computing

GPU acceleration of core ONETEP functionality is ongoing, focusing on GPU acceleration of sparse linear algebra operations which have been identified as the current bottleneck. Manuel dos Santos Dias is currently working on an improved GPU dispatch plan to minimise the number of host/device memory transfers. The next task is to tackle the GPU acceleration of band structure unfolding calculations.

Progress has also been made in the 'energy-efficiency' semi-direct integrals project in CRYSTAL by core-support team member Dr Barry G Searle: the code works, it now needs some benchmarking to adjust the cost function that decides whether to store or recompute an integral.

4. Current plans, developments, or specific applications of AI

CCP9 is preparing a special meeting of the working group to prepare a common strategy for AI in electronic structure/condensed matter theory.

5. Up to 5 research outputs that create an impact story for your community from the reporting period

An important paper linking RIXS and INS experiments for studying magnetism was published by Dr Manuel dos Santos Dias:

Hangyu Zhou, Manuel dos Santos Dias, Shijian Bao, Hanchen Lu, Youguang Zhang, Weisheng Zhao & Samir Lounis, "Triple-Q state in magnetic breathing kagome lattice", npj Spintronics 3, 31 (2025),
 [2]<https://doi.org/10.1038/s44306-025-00098-9>
 Collaboration with Beihang University (China), Forschungszentrum Jülich (Germany) and Martin-Luther-University Halle-Wittenberg (Germany).

6. Workshops and new opportunities*

CCP9 will meet for a large 3-day in-person "CCP9 Conference and Community Meeting" 21-14 April 2026, in Liverpool. We expect 100+ participants for this major event with a mix of established staff talks and focus sessions for younger researchers and community discussion. Registration will open early in the new year.

"Tackling the Many-Body Problem in Condensed Matter with Quantum Computing", organised by CCP-QC with support from CCP9 is to be held 1-3 July 2026.

"TYC 8th Energy Materials Workshop: From Electron and Phonon Interactions to Net Zero", organised by the Thomas Young Centre with support from CCP9 is to be held 1-3 July 2026.

"Recent Appointees in Physical Chemistry 2026 RAPC-RSC2026", supported by CCP9, is to be held 7-9 September 2026 (more information here <https://rapc-rsc2026.github.io/>).

7. Issues and problems*

None to report.

Biological Science

CCP-EM for the Period 31/05/2025 to 01/11/2025

Dr. Martyn Winn, CoSeC PI

Prof. Maya Topf, Chair of CCPEM, Dr. Tom Burnley, CoSeC Project Lead

1. Background

CCP-EM brings together a diverse and rapidly growing community of researchers involved in cryogenic electron microscopy. Software development is focussed on a suite of software that implements structure determination by single particle analysis and subtomogram averaging, including the interpretation of maps in terms of atomic models. The suite includes contributions from many collaborating groups in the UK and worldwide. Recently, we have implemented the ccpem-pipelinier framework which supports metadata management in workflows, archiving and deposition in the public repositories EMPIAR/EMDB/PDB. The Doppio user interface sits on top of the ccpem-pipelinier framework, with the Javascript framework allowing web-based operation and remote submission of compute jobs. CCP-EM organise and/or support a wide variety of training activities, with the annual Spring Symposium attracting over 350 in-person delegates. Machine learning techniques are ubiquitous in the current suite and in our future plans, for example implementing operations such as object recognition, classification and denoising, to name a few.

2. Highlights for the current reporting period

Grant renewal awarded: Core funding secured by MRC Partnership grant “Collaborative Computational Project for cryo electron microscopy (CCP-EM): expanding the reach of cryoEM” (~3FTEs, 2026-2031).

Software: Doppio v1.3 was released on 14/05/25 and Doppio v1.4 is scheduled for release by the end of October 2025. 1.4 contains the following updates:

Doppio changes

- New doppio-ssh script for automatic ssh port forwarding
- Added ability to continue and overwrite jobs
- Improved behaviour when changing job aliases
- Moorhen version updated to 0.19.1
- Improved isolation of Doppio’s Conda environment
- Improved external tool launching
- Packaging improvements
- Developer start-up improvements
- Various minor bug fixes and updates

Job changes

Added processing of predicted models to AlphaFold fetch job
 Added graphical outputs to Topaz training job
 Improve B-factor distribution and FSC plots in Validation and Servalcat jobs
 Updates to LocScale, ModelCraft and EMplacement jobs

Pipeliners changes

Removed requirement for job.star files' names to end with '_job'
 Fixed symlinks causing errors in job clean up
 Added ability for specific commands in some jobs to fail without failing the entire job
 Various minor bug fixes and updates

Full release notes here: https://www.ccpem.ac.uk/docs/doppio/release_notes.html

DRI-IMB: CCP-EM is a member of the “Digital Research Infrastructure for Integrative Molecular Biology” (DRIIMB) collaboration, alongside CCP4, CCPN and CCPBioSim, funded by the CoSeC bridging call to look at methods for integration across structural biology.

As part of Workpackage 2 “Linking MD simulations to cryo-EM”, Joel Greer is working on tools for assessing heterogeneous reconstruction in cryoEM which can describe discrete or continuous variation in molecular structures. Together with collaborators in the US, a community challenge will be launched in October/November 2025. Joel has been working with colleagues from CCPBioSim to generate ground truth data from MD simulations of selected biomolecules and was recently awarded the “CoSeC Early Career Researcher Award 2025 “. We will also contribute to WP4.2 “Scoping common data formats”, together with CCP4, which will look at joint refinement of atomic models against cryoEM and crystallographic data, using the interactive Moorhen graphics platform. We have worked with CCP4 chair Prof. Ivo Tews to recruit a PDRA to work on this project starting from January 2026.

Work is in progress for the 12th **Spring Symposium** to be held at the East Midlands Conference Centre, 22-24 April 2025. Talks from the 11th edition are now available on the CCP-EM YouTube channel <https://www.youtube.com/@ccpem7128/playlists>

Recent / upcoming workshops:

May 2025 CCP-EM WG 1 Meeting, Zoom, UK
 Jun 2025 UK CryoEM Facilities Meeting, Warwick, UK
 Jun 2025 KMUTT EM Workshop, Bangkok, Thailand
 Jul 2025 Integrative structural biology, Padua, Italy
 Aug 2025 BCA Summer School, York, UK
 Sep 2025 EMBO Workshop, Birkbeck, UK
 Sep 2025 National Facility for Protein Science, Shanghai, China
 Sep 2025 Doppio Roadshow, Imperial, UK
 Oct 2025 Icknield Model Building Workshop, RAL, UK
 Nov 2025 Doppio Roadshow, University of Manchester, UK

Nov 2025 CCP4/CCP-EM School Santiago - Structural Biology at the Foot of the Andes, Chile

CCP-EM are also sponsoring and speaking at the “Grand Opening of the Northern Eye, a 100 kV Tundra cryo-TEM in Newcastle University” on the 5th November 2025.

Training courses are usually run using the STFC Data Analysis as a Service (DAaaS) training system, running on STFC Cloud VMs (with or without GPU) and with Doppio and example data pre-installed. User access managed through DAaaS training website and proxy. The Doppio app runs in the user’s local browser giving a faster response than a remote desktop. We find this a very good way of running training courses.

In addition to software training CCP-EM organised the first UK CryoEM Facilities meeting. This was aimed at UK facility managers, and related staff, to share good practices and solve common challenges. It was well received and attended (~40 people), and we aim to organise follow-up meeting in 2027.

FAIR data: We are members of the Chan Zuckerberg Institute for Advanced Biological Imaging working group on tomography metadata. We are developing the TomoBabel library (with CZII, EMBL-EBI and CNB-CSIC Madrid, <https://github.com/TomoBabel>) and are now working on metadata converters for specific software packages. Matt Iadanza from the CCP-EM group received a ~£150k grant from the Silicon Valley Community Foundation/CZI to fund the completion of this project.

Green: Tom Burnley is part of a working group with others in the cryoEM field (from Leeds, Cambridge, Thermo Fisher) to quantify the carbon usage per experiment and make recommendations to help users to be environmentally sustainable. Initial findings were presented at the CCP-EM Spring Symposium in April.

3. Overview of work relating to accelerated computing

Different components of the CCP-EM software suite can make use of GPUs, OpenMP and MPI, although in general the software doesn’t scale to more than a few nodes. To-date, concerns have centred on memory and storage requirements, but work is planned to look at ways to speed up key steps in the cryoEM pipeline. Work in the Excalibur project “ExaBioSim” has included initial benchmarking of the Relion software for reconstruction. An initial 6-month pilot project with Oxford RSE Group and DLS/STRUBI (Feb-Aug 25) has been extended for further 6 months to continue benchmarking and GPU profiling of Relion (benchmarks have been made public). Future work will look to optimise use of GPUs, and to provide the user with recommended program parameters based on available hardware and a database of previous runs.

4. Current plans, developments, or specific applications of AI

AI/ML techniques are in widespread use for interpreting large cryoEM datasets. There are several on-going AI projects including: (1) affinity-VAE for automatic clustering and classification of objects in cryoET tomograms; (2) cryoDANN (Domain Adversarial training of Neural Network) for particle selection as a refinement of the 2D

classification step for particle set cleaning; (3) a noise2noise implementation for denoising tomograms; (4) benchmarking of AI tools from a US collaborator (BBSRC funding).

5. Up to 5 publications that create an impact story for your community from the reporting period

“PERC: a suite of software tools for the curation of cryoEM data with application to simulation, modelling and machine learning” B Costa-Gomes, J Greer et al., Acta F, October 2025

<https://journals.iucr.org/f/issues/2025/10/00/ir5046/>

“Affinity-VAE: incorporating prior knowledge in representation learning from scientific images” M Famili, J Mirecka et al. ECCV2024 proceedings, May 2025

https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-031-91721-9_12

“Roodmus: a toolkit for benchmarking heterogeneous electron cryo-microscopy reconstructions” M Joosten, J Greer, J Parkhurst, T Burnley and A J Jakobi *IUCr* November 2024 <https://doi.org/10.1107/S2052252524009321>

6. Workshops and new opportunities*

- Nov 2025 Protein Structure Determination in Industry (PSDI), invited workshop lecture
- Nov 2025 Grand Opening of the Northern Eye, Newcastle, CCP-EM Sponsorship, Matt Iadanza invited talk
- Mar 2026 CCP-EM Model Building Workshop, Bangalore, India
- April 2026 12th CCP-EM Symposium, EMCC, UK
- June 2026 NEMI Dutch cryoEM School, Delft/Utrecht
- June 2026 International School of Crystallography, Erice, Italy (<https://crystalalice.org/2026/programme.php>)
- Sep 2026 MSCDA cryoEM course, Exeter, UK
- Sep 14-16th Heterogeneity challenge, Cosener's, UK

7. Issues and problems*

Nothing specific.

CCPBioSim for the Period 01/04/2025 to 30/09/2025

Prof. Sarah Harris, Chair of CCP-BioSim

Dr. James Gebbie-Rayet, CoSeC Project Lead

1. Background

CCPBioSim is the Collaborative Computational Project in biomolecular simulation at the physics - life sciences interface, bringing together chemists, physicists and chemical engineers as well as researchers from all branches of "molecule-oriented" biochemistry and biology. Simulations help to analyse how enzymes catalyse biochemical reactions, and how proteins adopt their functional structures e.g. within

cell membranes. They contribute to the design of drugs and catalysts, and in understanding the molecular basis of disease. Our aim is to involve experimentalists and computational specialists in this work, sharing the belief that the best science can be done when theory and experiment are closely integrated. CCPBioSim engages with early career researchers and non-experts through the provision of tutorials and workshops enabling them to become proficient and productive users of biomolecular simulation techniques. We are also actively engaged in developing new advanced methods, which in future will be used by our community to deliver new and exciting science. We run a series of specialised industrial engagement seminars designed to bring industry researchers together to showcase their work, which is often very different from academia. CCPBioSim now also has a partnership with structural biology CCPs (CCP4, CCPEM and CCPN) in the DRI funded initiative DRIIMB to look at integrative molecular biology and the problems around software interoperability.

2. Highlights for the current reporting period

CCPBioSim has run three conferences this reporting period, the first being the Manchester Multiscale Conference (jointly with CCP5) 30 March – 2 April 2025, 86 people came in person and 16 registered to listen to the talks online. Our annual conference: Frontiers in Biomolecular Simulation, 14 – 16 July 2025. Held in Southampton and 104 people attended. We contributed a CECAM Flagship Workshop on Entropy of Soft Matter Systems, 27 – 29 August 2025. This meeting in Vienna, Austria was co-sponsored and organised by CCPBioSim and was arranged to coincide with the release of our new flagship software (CodeEntropy), which was unveiled at the conference. 30 people came to present and discuss entropy and the software used to calculate entropy from simulations. As a result of discussions at the meeting, we are now starting work on a scientific benchmarking exercise which will be published as a software review article.

CodeEntropy (<https://github.com/CCPBioSim/CodeEntropy>) has been the focus of the EPSRC funded part of our CoSeC support. With efforts in the reporting period focussed on preparation and testing for the first public stable release in August. Significant changes in the codebase were made in this period to ensure the theory and implementation matched and verified by testing and validation, since combining two separate codes into a single, posed significant challenges around the theory. The unification into a single software package that implements a full multi-scale description of orientational, vibrational and translational entropy has been successful. Further new features have been added to expand the quality of the output including an intuitive user input interface, categorised outputs and also a simple scheme for reducing the compute load when only averages for molecular environments are needed. We collaborated with HECBioSim CoSeC support to implement a parallel computing model for the heaviest part of the codebase that calculates the orientational entropy for water. CodeEntropy is a greener alternative to the current state of the art in running Free Energy based calculations to obtain entropy data, since it can be run as an analytical post-processing step to conventional MD simulations which are 10x less computationally intensive to run than the former. The code version 1.0.0 was

released on time at the CECAM Flagship Entropy Workshop in Vienna with already significant interest from industrial users.

In the DRIIMB part of CCPBioSim and at the CCPEM interface, work is focussed on bringing simulation-based dynamics to experimental data processing workflows by making tools interoperable. Work started with testing and identifying issues in a number of existing EM-guided MD workflow protocols for suitability (tempy-reff, MDFF, gromacs density-guided simulations). Work has begun on developing an advanced simulation focussed workflow builder to prepare molecular simulations from CryoEM derived structures (mdprep), this tool focussed on missing functionality in the above tools such as adding missing loops, renaming residues for MD engine compatibility and resolving steric clashes. Work has begun to identify routes to enhance experimental data by building on mdprep by for example benchmarking various methods for ensemble reweighting.

In the DRIIMB part of CCPBioSim and at the CCPN interface, work is focussed on developing an integrated workflow for NMR-restrained molecular dynamics (MD) simulations that bridges experimental NMR with atomistic simulation methods. The workflow pipeline automates structure preparation, restraint integration, and simulation execution across HPC environments such as NMRbox and SCARF, supporting both CPU and GPU back-ends. This approach enables reproducible, large-scale ensemble simulations. Post-processing and validation are performed using MDAnalysis, MDTraj, and cpptraj to compute RMSD, RMSF, S^2 order parameters, and NOE violation statistics. The workflow yields quantitative agreement between simulated ensembles and experimental NMR observables, ensuring data-driven refinement of structural ensembles. Overall, this framework provides a reproducible, FAIR and compliant bridge between NMR experiment and molecular simulation, aligning with the broader goals of the DRI-IMB and CCPBioSim communities to enable interoperable, experiment-integrated biomolecular modelling and will soon be made publicly available through the CCPBioSim GitHub repository.

The DRIIMB seminar by Brinda Vallet from PDB on 9 July 2025 had 51 attendees.

Sarah Harris (who gave a talk) and Julien Michel (session Chair) attended the Royal Society discussion meeting on applications of quantum computing in chemistry simulations: <https://royalsociety.org/science-events-and-lectures/2025/10/quantum-computing/>

The community agreed that better communication between quantum computing and domain experts was essential for progress to be made, and this is planned for the future.

3. Overview of work relating to accelerated computing

CCPBioSim as a consortium does not directly conduct activities that purely focus upon accelerated computing. However, the community has strong direct connections to the HECBioSim consortium which focuses on access to current UK HPC resources, optimising and benchmarking codes for such platforms. CCPBioSim are obviously an

important influence in the activities of the HEC since its members are the underlying driver as consumers of existing and future UK HPC. Our community as a whole have been engaging in the porting to and further optimisation of our codes for around a decade already so have significant experience in this area. Our community plan to engage with the next generation platforms such as ISAMBARD-3 and DAWN for applications around AI driven molecular simulations. We will continue to develop our new methodologies with these HPC capabilities from the concept stage and involving the HECBioSim CoSeC staff when needed. As part of the UKRI-DRI funded DRIIMB we plan to share our expertise in HPC across the experimental communities (CCP4, CCPEM and CCPN) that have come together to form the combined community with CCPBioSim.

4. Current plans, developments, or specific applications of AI

CCPBioSim is the focus community of a partner project (BioSimDB) within the UKRI and EPSRC jointly funded PSDI programme. BioSimDB is an initiative to build national data infrastructure for the deposition, sharing and curation of biomolecular simulation data to satisfy the principles of FAIR. CCPBioSim is driving the developments in this programme and the community is the user testbed for innovations that emerge in this area. CCPBioSim has been involved with the development of prototype of future metadata standards and an ontology for biomolecular simulation and has had a significant role in bringing the BioSimDB efforts together with the EU funded programme MDDB. The work in this area is expected to lead to key national capability in data that will underpin the future proliferation of advanced AI technologies that consume dynamics-based simulation data from our field. The principles and tooling that is emerging from the BioSimDB initiative are actively being included in the software development activities for both the EPSRC and DRI funded parts of CoSeC, which means any new software will be compatible with this new infrastructure out of the box.

5. Up to 5 research outputs that create an impact story for your community from the reporting period

CodeEntropy was released in August at the CECAM Flagship Workshop in Vienna. This new code is now publicly available and is expected to have significant interest from academic and industrial researchers working in drug discovery. Due to the fact that Entropy is often missing in drug discovery research, mainly due to incomplete theory and being very expensive to calculate only parts of the true picture. This new method offering a more complete description of the theory and running as an analytical procedure at the end of a conventional MD simulation, gives this method significant potential to disrupt the current state of the art in this crucial industry.

6. Workshops and new opportunities*

Events that are announced are here www.ccpbiosim.ac.uk/events/upcoming-events

In planning are:

- 10 new Industry Talks taking us to the end of 2026
- Possible ChemShell training in the spring

- Introduction of an intensive school format (potentially on DNA across scales including ohmics - not confirmed)
- Workshop on the use of biomolecular simulations with scattering experiments (planned for May in Leeds).
- Possible Cytosim modelling workshop aimed at experimental researchers
- Training Week 2026 to be confirmed (likely October, in Sheffield)
- DRIIMB large community meeting on data standards and sharing, planned for autumn 26, possibly in Windsor.

7. Issues and problems*

None

CCP4 for the Period 01/06/2025 to 01/11/2025

Prof. Ivo Tews, Chair of CCP4

1. Background

CCP4 provides and supports an integrated suite of programs for determination of macromolecular structures by X-ray crystallography. CCP4

- develops cutting edge approaches to experimental determination and analysis of macromolecular structures as a community-based resource;
- supports the development and integration of novel software into one suite;
- serves the widest possible research community, embracing academic (not for profit) and industrial (for-profit) research;
- offers education and training to scientists in experimental structural biology and encourages the wide dissemination of new ideas, techniques, and practice.

2. Highlights for the current reporting period

The CCP4 £2m BBSRC started in August 2024 and includes four work packages:

- **WP1** A statistical framework for analysing structural change and its representation in data (time and/or state); Hough, Evans, Winter, Diamond Light Source; PDRA Rachel Tang has started 30/09/2024; PI Winter has taken a new position with the Advanced Photon Source, and left the project; he is replaced by PI James Beilsten-Edmunds; PI Evans will retire in 2026, new PI tba.
- **WP2** Joint refinement of related structures; Murshudov, LMB Cambridge; Agirre, York; Tews, Southampton; Orville, Southampton, Diamond Light Source; PDRA Martin Malý has started 22/11/2024.
- **WP3** Advance computational methods for data processing and structure solution to exploit advantages in electron diffraction; Krissinel, Waterman; Research Complex at Harwell; PDRA Martin Petrovic started 01/07/2025.
- **WP4** Exploiting Deep Learning-based structural bioinformatics for crystallography; Rigden; Liverpool; PDRA Aderik Verspoels has started 16/09/2024.

The collaboration contract between the seven participating institutions was signed 14/02/2025. The grant team consisting of all hired PDRAs and all grant PIs met at a first kick-off meeting 27/11/2024. To foster collaboration, a slack channel was created in January 2025. The grant team meet twice in person at the CCP4 study weekend (January) and at the Developers meeting (July), where they also report to the CCP4 executive.

The “Digital Research Infrastructure for Integrative Molecular Biology (DRIIMB)”, funded since 11/2024, is meeting monthly as a consortium of CCP4 with CCPEM (who presently chair), CCPBioSim and CCPN. CCP4 has two work packages with two posts associated with this proposal, and we have now hired Dr Toby King for the project of data integration across different experimental techniques. See also sections 3 and 4.

3. Overview of work relating to accelerated computing

The CoSeC post Dr Daniel Celis Garza has reported marginal gains in the work associated with WP4 in the DRIIMB CoSeC bridging grant, as a pilot in heterogeneous computing. Results will be summarised in the next report.

4. Current plans, developments, or specific applications of AI

Two of the work packages of the BBSRC funded CCP4 grant explore AI:

- WP3 Methods for electron diffraction data for the refinement of macromolecular structures, using machine learning approaches to filter out dynamical scattering, and procedures for taking crystal defects and inelastic scattering terms into account.
- WP4 Exploiting Deep Learning-based structural bioinformatics: use of covariance-based distance and contact predictions to validate protein and nucleic acid structures; development of rational editing of RNA models for molecular replacement.

Additionally, in the DRIIMB CoSeC bridging grant we will explore the potential of AI/ML-based assessments of candidate Molecular Replacement solutions to outperform the conventional scoring methods based on root mean squared deviations (RMSD) template and target datasets.

Dr Toby King who joins the data integration project shared between CCP4 and CCPEM brings in expertise in AI.

5. Up to 5 research outputs that create an impact story for your community from the reporting period

In 2025, the primary publication for CCP4 (Acta Crystallogr D Struct Biol. 2023, 79:449-461. doi: 10.1107/S2059798323003595) has been cited 172 times. There are many high impact publications on scientific application of the software, including in Nature-, Science- and Cell-group journals. Further citations accumulate also in the field of AI use, in particular with respect of the use of AlphaFold in structural Biology (FEBS Open Bio 2025, 15:202-222, <https://doi.org/10.1002/2211-5463.13902>; Acta Crystallogr D

Struct Biol. 2025, 81:4-21, <https://doi.org/10.1107/S2059798324011999>;
Bioinformatics 2025, 41:btaf115, DOI 10.1093/bioinformatics/btaf115).

6. Workshops and new opportunities*

See here: <https://www.ccp4.ac.uk/workshops/>

The CCP4 study weekend held in January each year is a highlight event and of interest for other communities; attendance gives opportunity for cross community (net-)working, but online participation is also possible. The meeting gives a good overview on current trends.

Meetings coming up are:

2025

- Diamond Light Source 24-28 Nov
- AsCA, Taipei, 1 Dec

2026

- Study Weekend January
- Developers meeting – July
- SWSBC Portsmouth July
- BCA Summer School, York 31 July – 8 Aug
- Northern Meeting September

7. Issues and problems*

CCP4 needs to integrate new methodology in quantum crystallography and will participate at a DRIIMB funded workshop in 2026 (planning stage). The aim is to reach convergence of crystallographic techniques with quantum mechanics and directly use these methods in structure refinement of macromolecular structures.

The CCP4 Equity, diversity & inclusion team are now working on the ED&I roadmap for fairness in funding.

Contract issues like multi-party agreements take time and do not allow us to hire immediately into research grants that have been awarded. Contracts do seem to take a very long time to be finalised.

Computational Engineering

CCP-WSI for the Period 1/5/2025 to 31/10/2025

Prof. Deborah Greaves, Chair of CCP-WSI

1. Background

The CCP in Wave Structure Interaction (WSI) began in October 2015 and was extended in October 2020 through the successful CCP-WSI+ proposal. The aim is to bring

together and expand the national community of academics and industrial partners, working collaboratively on activities with a shared objective of building a Numerical Wave Tank (NWT) facility for the simulation of free-surface flow phenomena and fluid-wave interactions with complex structures. A range of networking activities, including focus groups, workshops, and road-mapping exercises, will provide a framework for innovation and the development of strategic software. The goal is to develop a robust and efficient computational WSI modeling tool capable of reliably quantifying wave-induced loads and the corresponding structural mechanics to supplement laboratory and field measurements early in the design process of associated structures. Throughout the project, with the assistance of CoSeC support (2.0 FTE), numerical modelers and experimentalists will combine their expertise to develop an open-source framework using state-of-the-art code coupling and parallelization practices. This will enable the inclusion of highly nonlinear and multi-physics effects in simulations while reducing the overall computational effort required. The software, held in a central code repository, will be professionally engineered, maintainable, and future-proof. It will also be tested and validated against measurement data from new fundamental benchmarking experiments. The project will provide advanced training in computational science and software development, as well as deliver outreach activities for schools and the general public.

2. Highlights for the current reporting period

During this reporting period, a series of virtual meetings of the CCP-WSI Working Group were held to discuss the CCP-WSI and HEC-WSI progress and activities.

Further meetings were held, between the CCP Chair and the CoSeC team associated with the CCP-WSI+ funding, focusing on the three key work packages: code coupling, parallel optimization, and sustaining outputs.

A two-year CCP-WSI Bridging Fund project co-led by the University of Plymouth and CoSeC is underway, aiming to enhance predictive capabilities in wave-structure interaction through AI-driven modelling. With CoSeC Core support, the work focuses on (i) developing AI-based reduced order models for FOWT simulations, and (ii) applying dimensionality reduction techniques to high-fidelity CFD datasets. The project includes over 35,000 node hours on ARCHER2 allocated via HEC-WSI. Key deliverables include training datasets, comparative studies on decoupled/coupled AI-ML model architectures, and journal publications on reduced-order modelling and dimensionality reduction methods.

The CCP-WSI Blind Test Series 5 workshop with topic sloshing in cylindrical tank, has been completed successfully at 19/9/2025 online, 41 participants from all around the world attend this workshop. Different numerical methods are presented and discussed. The physical data used in the blind test is shared. The dataset includes the time series for the assessment criteria, along with video data for each of the cases.

The Special Issue on “Sloshing of Liquid Hydrogen Fuel Tanks” in Ocean Engineering. This special issue will include papers arising from the blind test as well as broader

studies related to liquid hydrogen sloshing, including experimental, numerical, and theoretical research. Contributions addressing modelling methods, validation and design implications are all warmly welcomed.

The WSI community, in collaboration with OpenCFD Ltd, developed modifications enabling OpenFOAM to interface with the Multiscale Universal Interface (MUI) library. This allows coupling with external solvers without modifying OpenFOAM's source code. The contribution, now integrated upstream, has been integrated in OpenFOAM v2506 which was released in June 2025, greatly enhancing modular multi-physics and multi-scale simulation capabilities.

The CCP-WSI+ interacts with the eCSE-funded gpuFoam project lead by Prof Gavin Tabor (CCP-WSI co-I). gpuFoam is a research software engineering project to port the popular CFD code OpenFOAM to GPU platforms, of considerable interest given the use of OpenFOAM in WSI. The gpuFoam project is advancing well with core aspects of the code (main matrix solver routines and some boundary conditions) having been ported already; the aim is to complete and release at least two OpenFOAM solver codes, icoFoam and simpleFoam, by the end of the project (summer 2026).

2 summer internship (8 weeks) students are supported to create immersive visualisation of the coupled CFD simulation of a floating offshore wind turbine. The project explored Unity-based workflows to address latency issues in ParaView during animated sequences. A functional VR-ready demonstration was developed, alongside a reproducible workflow to support future outreach and stakeholder engagement

The CCP-WSI YouTube Channel now has 1,820 views and 48 subscribers. The CCP-WSI Organisation on GitHub has 9 repositories, 111 members and 14 followers. The CCP-WSI Organisation on GitHub current contains 16 benchmarking test cases.

The combined CCP-WSI, HEC-WSI and SIG-WSI mailing list has 210 members. The HEC-WSI currently supports 23 sub-groups: 8 Institutions and 15 projects, with 60 active users from 21 organisations. In this reporting period, the CCP-WSI website has received 7114 page views from 1200 users over 1640 sessions. The WSI Catalogue has received 1700 page views from 462 users over 908 sessions.

The CCP-WSI Catalogue: Poulter, G. delivered a talk entitled "Research Object Cataloguing" at CoSeC Communities Forum on 4 June 2025. The presentation was based on the case study: Towards a catalogue for CoSeC to enhance discoverability and collaboration ([CoSeC, June 25, 2025](#))

3. Overview of work relating to accelerated computing

Currently HEC-WSI has 16 active subgroups, 68 members. In the past 6 months, 106,187.313 CUs (128 core*hour per CU as the ARCHER2 definition) have been used, with 20,632 jobs submitted on ARCHER2

4. Current plans, developments, or specific applications of AI

The CCP-WSI team has planned the upcoming CCP-WSI Hackathon, with the schedule currently under discussion.

The CCP-WSI Focus Group Workshop 5 facilitated a broad discussion on grand challenges in the field. Building on these outcomes, the CCP-WSI team plans to convene a meeting to discuss and finalise the roadmap for integrating AI into Wave-Structure Interaction (WSI) research.

Building on CoSeC's evaluation of AI/ML approaches, the Research Technical Professional (RTP), with support from CoSeC, plans to integrate AI models to replace traditional solvers within a coupled CFD–CSM computational model of floating offshore wind turbines (FOWTs). The coupling will be achieved via the ParaSIF framework and embedded within a FOWT surrogate model. Both implicit AI-based surrogates and non-intrusive reduced-order modelling techniques will be explored to enhance computational efficiency.

5. Up to 5 research outputs that create an impact story for your community from the reporting period

Stella et al. (2025) 'How Transparent is Water? Addressing Ethical Concerns in AI Surrogate Development for Nearshore Wave Modelling and the Natural Sciences', *Journal of Ethics in Entrepreneurship and Technology*. (accepted).

Brown, S. (Creator), Colville, S. (Creator), Lee, Y. C. (Creator) & Greaves, D. (Creator), 6 Oct 2025. Isothermal sloshing in a circular tank (CCP-WSI Test Case 017 Dataset), University of Plymouth,
DOI: 10.24382/1648f8b5-5582-44e5-8e6f-8f95c360b339, https://ccp-wsi.ac.uk/catalogue/test_cases/test_case_017

Poulter, G. (2025), 'Towards a catalogue for CoSeC to enhance discoverability and collaboration', presentation at CoSeC Communities Forum, 4 June 2025.

Mayank Kumar, Jony Castagna, Mattijs Janssens, Raynold Tan, Wendi Liu and Gavin Tabord. (2025), 'Porting OpenFOAM on GPU via modern C++', parCFD2025.

6. Workshops and new opportunities*

25-26 November: MRP Workshop: Developing a Roadmap for Evidence-Based Decision Support Tools for Offshore Wind Farms. Location Plymouth

CCP-WSI Hackathon (Date TBC): A community-focused, hands-on coding event currently under planning. The event is expected to take place within the next 12 months, with details to be confirmed in upcoming CCP-WSI coordination meetings.

International Workshop (2026 Q3): One international workshop will be hosted to build engagement with PRACE/Euro HPC Exascale and the international standards (IEA, IEC, ITTC, etc) community.

CCP Conference: CCP-WSI will collaborate with other CCP communities to deliver a joint CCP Conference, providing a platform for sharing best practices, fostering cross-community collaboration, and strengthening collective impact

Where applicable, highlight events of potential interest for other communities and opportunities for cross community working.

7. Issues and problems*

PI is moving to Oxford University in February 2026

CCP Turbulence for the Period 01/04/2025 to 30/09/2025

Prof. Sylvain Laizet, Chair of CCP Turbulence

1. Background

No changes to previous

2. Highlights for the current reporting period

- CoSeC have awarded the 2025 CoSeC Impact Award to Dr David Lusher of the Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency (JAXA) for his exceptional contributions to the scientific community. Dr Lusher is the co-creator and lead developer of OpenSBLI, one of the flagship solvers supported by the CCP Turbulence.
- The UK Turbulence Consortium secured some funding with UKRI to launch a UK AI Hub for Turbulence.
- A training session was organised in September 2025 around OPS, OpenSBLI and SENGAs, some of the software supported by the CCP Turbulence.
- An advanced developer meeting for Xcompact3d was organised in May 2025 to discuss about the future of the solver.
- Continuous maintenance and support activities: This task is dealing with software sustainability. With a constantly evolving HPC landscape, it is crucial to make sure that the features already available in our flow solvers are optimised, reliable and robust enough to be compatible with the latest versions of libraries and compilers.
- Implementation of particle tracking capabilities in OPS.
- Development of a new version of 2DECOMP&FFT in C++ with a multi-backend approach for use on CPUs and GPUs.
- On-going work on building a FAIR Data Repository framework for the UK Turbulence Consortium community with InvenioRDM and Ceph.

3. Overview of work relating to accelerated computing

- On-going work around SENGAs and OpenSBLI to make these solvers suitable for large-scale heterogeneous computing via the use of OPS.
- Re-design of Xcompact3d using a multi-backend approach for large-scale heterogeneous computing.

4. Current plans, developments, or specific applications of AI

No activities related to AI as we are missing CoSeC support (0.5 FTE). We managed to secure some funding from UKRI for AI activities within the UK Turbulence Consortium community. A big workshop will be organised in January 2026 which will provide information for a white paper on the use of AI for turbulence research in the UK.

5. Up to 5 research outputs that create an impact story for your community from the reporting period

- Akkurt, S., Lemaire, S., Bartholomew, P., & Laizet, S. (2025). A distributed-memory tridiagonal solver based on a specialised data structure optimised for CPU and GPU architectures. *Computer Physics Communications*, 109747.
- All the publications from the UK Turbulence Consortium members who used ARCHER2 can be found here: <https://www.ukturbulence.co.uk/2025.html>

6. Workshops and new opportunities*

- Delivery of several invited talks at prestigious conference and for prestigious series of
- seminars.
- 2026 UK AI for Turbulence Workshop, January 26-27, 2026, in London.
- 2026 Annual meeting for the UK Turbulence Consortium community, March 26-27, 2026, in Edinburgh.

7. Issues and problems*

- Limited options to benchmark our software (at scale) on GPU nodes in the UK (Isambard AI and Dawn are for AI applications).
- End of the Tier2 systems in the UK and end of ARCHER2 (Nov 2026), with the new supercomputer planned for early 2027 in the most optimistic scenario.
- Lack of clarity about the future of the CoSeC support for CCP projects and lack of clarity about the future of the HEC consortia (after 2026).

CCP-NTH for the Period 01/04/2025 to 31/10/2025

Prof. Shuisheng He, Chair of CCP-NTH Chair

Dr. Wei Wang, CoSeC Project Lead

1. Background

No changes to previous

2. Highlights for the current reporting period

High-Fidelity Simulation Capabilities: Ongoing development of the community DNS solver CHAPSim2 has expanded its capabilities for nuclear thermal hydraulics and fusion energy research. Key achievements include re-implementation and validation of an immersed boundary method for complex geometries in the latest version, development of MHD support for duct flow simulations involving two pairs of parallel walls and enhanced on-the-fly post-processing capabilities that significantly reduce data communication, reprocessing requirements, and storage demands.

Green Computing Integration: High-performance computing efficiency has remained central to CHAPSim2 development, ensuring sustainable and energy-efficient computational workflows. Community members actively participate in workshops on energy-efficient computing and environmental sustainability, embedding green computing principles into both code development and simulation production practices.

FAIR Data Principles: A benchmark study on Reactor Vessel Auxiliary Cooling Systems (RVACS) has been completed and presented at an international conference in July. A journal paper is ready to submit for publication, with all benchmarking data prepared for open-sourcing and public dissemination via STFC Open Access, promoting transparency and data reusability in alignment with FAIR data principles.

3. Overview of work relating to accelerated computing

Work related to accelerated computing in the present project focuses on the GPU porting of CHAPSim2, which aims to extend this direct numerical simulation tool (originally designed for massively parallel CPU-based HPC systems) to modern heterogeneous platforms equipped with GPUs. Leveraging the GPU's exceptional efficiency in math-intensive operations, the new implementation will enable CHAPSim2 to tackle large-scale flow problems at affordable computational cost and with reasonable simulation turnaround times. The porting effort involves restructuring key parts of the code to minimise GPU memory usage and costly host-device data transfers. Large local arrays are replaced with shared global work arrays accessed via pointers, improving memory reuse across equations. Planned activities include scaling tests once the code is ready, followed by performance optimisation to fully exploit GPU capabilities.

4. Current plans, developments, or specific applications of AI

A detailed review of AI and machine learning (AI/ML) applications in nuclear engineering has been conducted. The review draws on four leading journals in the field and examines over 120 papers covering more than 15 research themes. Its aim is to provide a clear understanding of the rapidly growing developments in AI and their specific applications within nuclear engineering.

5. Up to 5 research outputs that create an impact story for your community from the reporting period

During this reporting period, CCP-NTH has focused on advancing high-fidelity simulation capabilities to investigate fundamental mechanisms in non-conventional fluids and heat transfer. Using the community solver CHAPSim2 developed under CCP-NTH, researchers have generated high-quality DNS data to support the community and enable future AI/ML applications in this field. The newly implemented immersed boundary method has been applied to investigate the effects of surface roughness, and the combined influence of roughness and buoyancy, on flow and heat transfer in fluids at supercritical conditions. Additionally, the solver's MHD functionality has enabled systematic investigation of magnetohydrodynamic effects under various operating conditions. This significant research was presented at NURETH21 in September 2025, the largest international conference in nuclear thermal hydraulics.

Beyond high-fidelity simulation, CCP-NTH continues to develop and apply cost-effective modelling techniques to address the complexities of nuclear reactor systems. Studies on Loss of Forced Cooling Accident (LOFA) conditions in High-Temperature Gas-Cooled Reactors (HTGR) were featured in ARCHER2 publications, demonstrating the practical application and impact of these computational methods in real-world nuclear safety scenarios.

Community engagement remained a priority during this period, with the largest CCP-NTH annual technical meeting to date held in Derby and co-hosted with Rolls-Royce. The event brought together researchers, industry practitioners, and stakeholders for in-depth technical discussions and knowledge exchange on the latest advances in nuclear thermal hydraulics. The meeting successfully strengthened cross-sector collaborations and reinforced CCP-NTH's mission to foster innovation and excellence in this critical research area.

6. Workshops and new opportunities*

Workshops, Conferences, and Training Activities (Next 12 Months):

- Fusion Thermal Hydraulics Challenge Workshop – 19 November 2025, Sheffield
- CCP-NTH Annual Technical Meeting – June 2026 (exact date to be confirmed)
- CCP-NTH AI4NTH Summer School – June/July 2026
- CCP-NTH Research Days – held regularly throughout the year (target: bi-monthly)
- CCP-NTH Webinars – held regularly throughout the year (target: monthly)
- CCP-NTH Developer Updates – held regularly throughout the year (target: weekly)

Workshops, conference and Training Activities (past 6 months):

- 6th Annual Technical Meeting of CCP-NTH (19-20 June 2025, Nuclear Skills Academy, Derby) Co-hosted by Rolls-Royce in collaboration with CCP-NTH, this event brought together over 60 leading experts from academia, industry, and government organisations.
- CCP-NTH supported up to five researchers to present their work at the 21st International Topical Meeting on Nuclear Reactor Thermal Hydraulics (NURETH-21)- the world's largest conference in this field-enhancing the visibility and engagement of the UK nuclear thermal-hydraulics community within the international research landscape.
- CCP-NTH supported members to attend Working Party on Scientific Issues and Uncertainty Analysis of Reactor Systems (WPRS) benchmark workshops organised by NEA and University of Cambridge to enhance knowledge exchange and potential international collaboration.
- CCP-NTH co-organised and co-sponsored EXCELLERAT Training on Advanced CFD and Turbulence Modelling, hosted by the Barcelona Supercomputing Centre (BSC) from 14-16 October 2025. The event provided participants with advanced knowledge in computational fluid dynamics and high-performance computing applications.
- CCP-NTH Developer Updates Meeting: Weekly organised to support code development
- CCP-NTH Research Days: Regularly organised to support early-career researchers in code development, application, and research within nuclear thermal hydraulics.
- Monthly CCP-NTH Webinars: Ongoing monthly sessions that promote knowledge exchange and discussion on the latest developments in nuclear thermal-hydraulics research and applications.

7. Issues and problems*

A GPU-enabled system with appropriate specifications is essential for code porting and testing. Currently, SCARF and STFC Cloud each provide four NVIDIA A100 GPUs (40 GB HBM2e), while the national system Cirrus offers four NVIDIA V100 GPUs (16–32 GB HBM2e). However, these freely accessible resources are becoming dated relative to current technology standards. To support continued development, testing, and

benchmarking activities, access to more modern, higher-performance GPU infrastructure is increasingly necessary.

Access to AI expertise from STFC remains limited, which continues to constrain progress on committed AI-related initiatives.

Tomographic Imaging

CCPi for the Period 01/04/2025 to 31/09/25

Prof. Philip Withers, Chair of CCPi Chair

Prof. William Lionheart, CCPi Co-Director

Dr. Jakob Jorgensen, International

Dr. Edoardo Pasca, CoSeC Project Lead

Dr. Martin Turner, CCPi Secretariat

1. Background *“No major changes to previous” minor (dates)*

The computational collaborative project in tomographic imaging (CCPi) was initiated in 2012 to support the UK nonclinical computed tomography (CT) community with the aim of: ‘Developing software and the necessary training to increase the quality and level of information that could be gleaned from X-ray projection data.’ Specifically, three suites of open-source software tools have been developed by CCPi in response:

1. simulation software for calibration, training, experiment planning, generation of data for development of methods and AI tools; and
2. software for pre-processing of raw CT data and reconstruction able to reconstruct a 3D/4D volume images from both standard and ‘sub-optimal’ datasets; and
3. quantification techniques to extract relevant quantities from 3D/4D data, such as Digital Volume Correlation.

This extensive python ecosystem supports CT users across a wide range of imaging devices including lab X-ray, national mid-scale research facilities and synchrotron X-ray and neutron CT. Our CoSeC support enables us to develop, maintain, and promote this CCPi Core Imaging Library (CIL) (release CIL v 25 in August, 2025) as well as a range of other related software; notably interactive visualisation and the iDVC (Digital Volume Correlation) code initiated as a result of CCPi funded international visits.

2. Highlights for the current reporting period

We report here on several community engagement events, over the reporting period, spanning the multiple CCPi supported codebases, all increasing the user and developer base. This participation exceeds the original CoSeC grant targets and those outlined in the 2018 EPSRC X-Ray CT roadmap.

In the past period we sponsored and supported the following events:

- Workshop and hackathon on Efficient integration of SIRF/STIR/CIL with Pytorch, 7-9 April 2025 UCL, London; to enable use of AI/ML tools within the codebases, such as deep learning denoisers.
- Supported multiple attendances to promote the codebase at our equivalent organisation in the United States, ToScA North America conference and NoCTURN; held at AMNH (American Museum of Natural History) New York USA; involving giving a CIL Training session 12 May 2025, ToScA NA presentations 13-14 May 2025 and active involvement with the co-located NoCTURN.org workshop, 15-16 May 2025
- iDVC training course was given at the University of Bath, 22 May 2025 and a CIL training course at the ToScA UK & Europe meeting, 10-12 September 2025, ESRF Grenoble France
- Supported and presented at both the 8th Workshop on Advances on X-Ray Imaging, held at Diamond Light Source, 24 June 2025 RAL and the Dimensional X-Ray CT Conference (d-XCT), 25-26 June 2025 held at WMG, University of Warwick, Coventry
- Attended the Energy Efficient Computing Workshop 15-16 September 2025, with related developers to discuss integration routes within the codebases.

During this reporting period we also finalised all commitments for the CCP Bridging Funding FY24-25 Additional Components (March-May 2025):

1. Funded coding project (University of Warwick), to investigate specific iterative solution that were presented in New York (ToScA NA) and at our local Show-and-Tell events (<https://www.ccpi.ac.uk/events/>) as well as planned presentations for the main CIL User Meeting in Jan 2026.

2. A workstation has been purchased with the scope of optimisation and testing of algorithms and general stress test of the software base. The workstation is now hosted at Harwell Research Complex, with extra storage being allocated and used on local and related datasets.

3. We gave bespoke training and presentations on this codebase along with the rest of the CCPi (Core Imaging Library) portfolio at ESRF and INSA-Lyon, France (February and September 2025).

Outreach: continual collaboration with the Mantid Imaging team (ISIS), the CIL team continue to exploit Tomography public engagement activities, which includes at various conference stands and at the DL open day in November 2025. A fortnightly CCPi Show-and-Tell online meeting is organised to strengthen the community bonds and foster exchange of ideas and information (in the period 16 short talks were given by users and developers).

Standards and support for Dimensional-XCT: Attended and voted on BSI / ISO standardisation WG10 meeting 3-5 March 2025 BSI Chiswick, London and 8-10 September 2025 in Harbin, China.

Training: The network carries out its own training courses on the main developed software; but also collates and advertises community training; notably linked through the NXCT.ac.uk, the University of Manchester at Harwell, and as recommended from the 2018 EPSRC X-Ray CT roadmap report.)

CIL Software: In the reporting period CIL has seen 2 stable releases. iDVC software: Version 25.0.0 of the iDVC digital volume correlation software has been released and code has been made Open Source.

3. Overview of work relating to accelerated computing

We have four outcomes on the current proposal that are all progressing, with specific software development coding outputs. Three are focussing on acceleration and optimisation:

1. *Utilise heterogeneous computing including new GPU architectures for increased software efficiency;*
2. *Incorporate fundamental algorithmic design including new optimisation methods;*
3. *Enable code optimisation for environmentally sustainable computational resources;*

A further outcome actively has been successfully utilising the STFC Cloud environment.

4. *Develop training platforms and learning tools based on cloud resources;*

4. Current plans, developments, or specific applications of AI

We held a workshop and hackathon on Efficient Integration of SIRF/STIR/CIL with Pytorch, to enable the better and more informed use of AI libraries within the CIL pipeline. The main aims are:

1. Enable the integration of AI/ML tools across the full XCT pipeline process via agnostic data containers, see [GitHub](#)
2. Strengthen integration with gVXR for the generation of labelled training data for AI methods training.
3. Test Plug and play methods, such denoisers, already publicly available, such as on DeepInv.

A follow-on Symposium on AI and Reconstruction for Biomedical Imaging, is planned for **9-10 March 2026** with CCPi supporting CCP SyneRBI

5. Up to 5 research outputs that create an impact story for your community from the reporting period

Highlight for this report period, are the recent key papers and training list for the Simulation software gVXR; which has been recognised with a community choice award by source forge, and awarded 3rd place for the Dirk Bartz Prize:

- <https://ccpi.ac.uk/gvirtualxray-recognised-with-community-choice-award-by-sourceforge/>
- <https://www.cosec.ac.uk/impact/ccpi-member-prof-franck-vidal-awarded-3rd-place-for-dirk-bartz-prize-2025/>

gVXR team have held two user training in 2025, STFC, Daresbury (about 10 scientists), INSA-Lyon, MatéIS (material science) and CREATIS (medical imaging) research groups (about 20 people, inc. PhD students, Postdocs, Scientists and Academics)

In the last year this has resulted in two community core review papers:

- Vidal, F. P., Afshari, S., Ahmed, S., Albiol, A., Albiol, F., Béchet, É., ... Villard, P.-F. (2025). X-ray simulations with gVXR in education, digital twinning, experiment planning, and data analysis. Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms, 568, 165804. doi:10.1016/j.nimb.2025.165804
 - Vidal, F. P., Afshari, S., Albiol, A., Albiol, F., Bellot, A. C., Brun, A. L., ... Villard, P.-F. (2025). Meuschke, M., & Kuhlen, T. W. (Eds.). X-ray simulations with gVirtualXray in medicine and life sciences. Dirk Bartz Prize for Visual Computing in Medicine and Life Sciences 2025 (Eurographics Medical Prize). The Eurographics Association. 3rd place. doi:10.2312/evm.20251974
- ... and 11 user papers.

6. Workshops and new opportunities*

A list of future workshop and conferences with a participation of CoSeC or CCPi:

- IBSim-4i, **20-23 October 2025**, held at the IoP London
- CT Public Engagement at Daresbury Laboratory, **28 October 2025** Part of the major Public Access Day
- Mantid User Workshop, **6-7 November 2025** CIL code integration
- Workshop on CT and DVC – with France, Bordeaux on **12 November 2025**
- Autumn CIL Hackathon; **18-21 November 2025** (“CIL CT Data Reader Hackathon”)
- CoSeC Conference **3 December 2025** where CIL presentations and posters are proposed
- CIL User Meeting, **27-30 January 2026**, Rutherford Appleton Laboratory
- Symposium on AI and Reconstruction for Biomedical Imaging, **9-10 March 2026** CCPi supporting CCP SyneRBI

A new XCT Roadmap is being planned with activities from **December 2025 to June 2026**. Previous roadmap was available, on the EPSRC website (2018 EPSRC X-Ray CT roadmap) and has informed projects over the last 7 years. Activities planned:

- Two Online Surveys for Future XCT uses and needs; one for the community and the other for the industrial contacts
- One-to-One interviews regarding specific contacts from survey responses.
- Three Town Hall meetings; one virtual; and the other two based in London and in Manchester.
- Report to be edited and published on a UKRI website dictating future vision including grand challenges.

7. Issues and problems*

Recruitment has stabilised, and we are always applying for extra funds across domains to supplement the DRI/STFC funding we currently have. A recent issue has been the unavailability of the STFC Cloud Infrastructure, which has been in the past very useful for user training, hackathons as well as testbed setups.

CCP SyneRBI for the Period 1/04/25 to 30/09/25

Dr. Evgueni Ovtchinnikov, STFC, Project Manager
Prof. Kris Thielemans, Chair of CCPSyneRBI

1. Background

For medical imaging, the UK is a globally leading country. The Collaborative Computational Project in Synergistic Biomedical Imaging (CCP SyneRBI), established in 2015 as CCP in Positron Emission Tomography and Magnetic Resonance imaging (CCP PETMR) and extended in 2020 under the new name, aims at bringing together the best of the UK's imaging expertise to capitalise on the investment in this area. Research has shown that the use of MRI intermediate results can improve PET image quality, and vice versa (in some cases), with some scanners capable of acquiring MR and PET data simultaneously. These techniques are now under investigation for PET and Single Photon Emission Computed Tomography (SPECT) in the context of Molecular Radio Therapy (MRT). The main deliverable of the project is an Open-Source reconstruction software framework we named SIRF (Synergistic Image Reconstruction Framework). SIRF is simple enough in use for educational and research purposes, thus reducing the "barrier for entry" for new contributors to imaging research and development, and at the same time powerful enough to process real scanner data. SyneRBI also contributes to other Open-Source projects, including STIR (Software for Tomographic Image Reconstruction) for PET and SPECT.

STFC CoSeC support for this CCP currently focusses on developing the SIRF and associated code base that provides an easy-to-use Python environment built around existing Open-Source reconstruction software. This includes maintaining network, website, running workshops and training courses, on top of the software engineering effort that contributes to SIRF development, testing, deployment and documentation.

2. Highlights for the current reporting period

2.1 Organisation of PET Rapid Image Reconstruction Challenge 2 and associated software, data and workshop.

One major activity in the current reporting period has been organising PETRIC2, the sequel of our PET Rapid Image Reconstruction Challenge which will run over the winter (November 2025 to 15 Feb 2026). Its primary aim will be to stimulate research into the development of fast PET image reconstruction algorithms applicable to real world data. Motivated by the success of the clinical translation of regularised image reconstruction in PET and other modalities, PETRIC2 will concentrate on reconstruction in a Maximum A Posteriori setting. The participants will have access to a sizeable set of phantom data acquired on a range of clinical scanners. Compared to PETRIC1, the data will be considerably noisier, i.e. corresponding to faster scans and/or lower injected radioactivity. The main task for the participants of the challenge will be to reach a solution which would be close to the converged target image (in terms of standard clinical measures) as quickly as possible (as measured in terms of computation time). This task therefore requires a balance between algorithm design and implementation optimisation. An example solution which reaches the target image quality but takes a long time will be provided at the beginning of the challenge.

2.1.1 PETRIC2 data.

The PET raw data will be pre-processed to enable researchers to take part even if they have little experience in handling real world data. The PETRIC pre-processed data is available at <https://petric.tomography.stfc.ac.uk/data/> (hosted by STFC). We are currently uploading raw and pre-processed data onto Zenodo to ensure future availability. A similar service will be set-up for PETRIC2.

2.1.2 PETRIC2 software.

New versions of our Open-Source software SIRF, STIR and CCPi Open-Source software CIL will be provided to develop and test the algorithms. The participants will be instructed to use STIR (via SIRF) projectors in their implementations, so that the reconstructed image quality and timing performance only depend on the reconstruction algorithm. Participants will have access to the source code, a docker image as well as the possibility to run reconstructions on the STFC Cloud.

Updated scripts for pre-processing scripts for PET raw data preparation, generating different noise levels etc are in preparation. All software will be available at <https://github.com/SyneRBI/PETRIC2/> and <https://github.com/SyneRBI/PETRIC-backend>.

2.2 Workshop and hackathon on Integration of libraries for physics informed deep learning in imaging

On 7 -9 Apr 2025, CCP SyneRBI and CCPi co-organised a workshop at UCL on Integration of libraries for physics informed deep learning in imaging and a hackathon

on STIR/SIRF/CIL integration with Python deep learning frameworks such as PyTorch. The workshop talks were presented by the main developers of major image reconstruction packages (including projects outside of the CCPs), which allowed comparing different approaches. This was then followed by a hackathon aim was the optimisation of the usage of CUDA in STIR/SIRF/CIL and other packages when interfacing to PyTorch.

The workshop and hackathon were attended by ~25 people in person. Remote attendance to the workshop was also possible. More information, including recordings of the presentations as available

at <https://www.ccp-synerbi.ac.uk/events/hackathon-on-pytorch/>.

2.3 Workshop and training at PET is Wonderful 2025

CCP SyneRBI co-sponsored the PET is Wonderful educational sessions in Edinburgh, see <https://petiswonderful.org/past-meetings/>. The sessions ran over 2 days and had international renowned speakers on a range of topics from radiochemistry, image reconstruction to clinical impact. The sponsoring was used to record and edit these educational talks, which will be made available on the Univ of Edinburgh training platform as well as the SyneRBI YouTube channel. In addition, SyneRBI organised a 1-day training school on practical aspects, attended by ~25 participants ranging from MSc students, clinical scientists to academic staff. Many of the trainers were past SyneRBI trainees.

2.4 Integration of PET and MR Raw data into an open database and management platform

Medical image data is commonly saved in widely accessible DICOM or NIFTI format. Raw data handling is much more challenging as there is little support apart from vendor-specific proprietary software tools. Together with a team from the Advanced Research Computing (ARC) centre at UCL plugins for XNAT, an open-source imaging informatics software platform, are being developed. These plugins will allow for the handling of MR and PET raw data and are an important step to be able to apply advanced image reconstruction techniques to clinical data in a transparent and easy-to-use environment.

2.5 Exchanges and visits

Matteo Colombo, PhD student, visited UCL for a 3-month exchange from the University of Milano-Bicocca to get experience with CUDA programming and optimise a part of the STIR code used for “regularisation” of the image reconstruction. This has resulted in major speed-up as well code simplification (pull request merged after this reporting period). Matteo gave a hybrid seminar on his progress, attended by ~35 researchers.

Zekai Li, PhD student, visited UCL for a 1-month exchange from the University of Groningen to work on testing and optimising reconstruction for Long Axial Field of View scanners, a major development in PET with large research impact. At the end of the

exchange, initial reconstructions of the Siemens Quadra were feasible, although work is still in progress. Zekai gave a hybrid seminar as well, attended by ~30 people. Christoph Kolbitsch from the Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt in Berlin, Germany will be spending a year in the UK working together with Kris Thielemans and David Atkinson (UCL) and Matt Hall and Matt Cashmore (NPL) on open-access reference data for image reconstruction. His aim is to obtain MR and PET-MR phantom and in-vivo data at multiple sites covering all major vendors, prepare this data for open-access publication and provide reference reconstructions for easy reuse.

3. Overview of work relating to accelerated computing

PET scanner geometry and physics makes the process of acquiring data inherently parallel, thus opening vast opportunities for the acceleration of image reconstruction by employing parallel computation on GPUs, many core CPUs and other modern high-performance architectures. STIR already benefits from these opportunities considerably, and our team relentlessly pursues further performance improvements. Our major recent achievement is a dramatic acceleration (10-200 times) of algebraic operations on data by minimizing memory transactions and restructuring code to enable compiler optimisations.

In addition, the computation of image operations for regularisation are being optimised (see M. Colombo's exchange visit above).

4. Current plans, developments, or specific applications of AI

We are in the final stages of the preparation of STIR 6.3 and SIRF 3.9, both releases with major improvements, ready for PETRIC2. Our next challenging task is to significantly reduce data transfer to/from GPU. We are investigating the use of CUDA managed pointers to minimise the necessary code changes, while enabling GPU-only computations in most cases. However, impact on processing with large data sizes will need to be investigated.

We have started with measuring impact of various computing methods using Code Carbon <https://codecarbon.io/>. This will ultimately lead to a comparison of energy use in terms of algorithms as well as computing architectures.

We have created initial examples of AI-enabled image reconstruction using Pytorch integration. These will need to be optimised using our latest advances in STIR and SIRF. We anticipate major developments in this area in our next hackathon (see below).

5. Up to 5 research outputs that create an impact story for your community from the reporting period

We have demonstrated that in the 3D cardio-respiratory motion compensation MRI reconstruction stochastic optimisation reduces the computation time of a factor 5 with respect to deterministic algorithms.

Letizia Protopapa et al Efficient motion-corrected image reconstruction for 3D cardiac MRI through stochastic optimisation 2025 Phys. Med. Biol. 70 185012

6. Workshops and new opportunities*

We are organising the following events in the next reporting period:

- The 4th hybrid hackathon event of the **Emission Tomography Standardization Initiative (ETSI)** Chiba, Tokyo, November 9-10th, 2025. This hackathon will allow us to finalise the proposed standard for PET Raw Data (PETSIRD), which will then be sent to final feedback to vendors and the larger community.
- **Symposium on AI and Reconstruction for Biomedical Imaging.** London Institute of Healthcare Engineering, March 9-10 2026. This two-day symposium will feature invited internationally leading researchers covering recent advances in AI and image reconstruction for biomedical imaging, and is intended to enhance UK and international networking, research progress and education in the AI as well as image reconstruction aspects of SyneRBI. At present we have 15 invited speakers, 40 submitted abstracts and 49 people registered, with more expected.
- After the symposium, we will hold a 2-day Hackathon on Software for Machine Learning Approaches for Reconstruction in Biomedical Imaging, following up on our previous hackathon. We aim to make considerable progress on integrating Machine Learning approaches into SIRF by connecting with AI/ML toolboxes such as from the **DeepInverse** project, who will send 2 of their developers to the hackathon.

7. Issues and problems*

The main stumbling block affecting our software development remains the installation of SIRF and its prerequisites under various Operating Systems. While we provide a Virtual Machine and docker containers, this is still a hurdle for many users. However, we are benefitting from work with CCPi to make installation easier (by integration with PyPI and conda).

We also have not yet succeeded in the Windows installation of Gadgetron. This is now unlikely to proceed as development of Gadgetron is frozen. The impact of this needs to be reviewed in the next reporting period.

Quantum Computing

CCP-QC for the Period 01/Apr/2025 to 30/Sep/2025

Prof. Viv Kendon, Chair of CCP-QC Chair

Dr. Paolo Emilio Trevisanutto, CCP-QC Secretary

1. Background

CCP-QC was started in 2019 with a remit to bring about close co-operation between other CCPs and the quantum computing community, rather than build a separate computational community for quantum computing. CCP-QC aims to:

1. Build an active research community encompassing CCP members interested in enhancing their simulations by adding quantum computing capability to their code, and quantum technology researchers working on applications of quantum computing to simulations;
2. Generate small projects supported by CoSeC staff time to develop methods appropriate to specific applications, leading to proof-of-concept demonstrations on early quantum hardware. This will also develop capacity in CoSeC for quantum computing;
3. Collaborate with the National Quantum Computing Centre (NQCC) and the Quantum Computing (QCi3) Hub in developing early applications of quantum computing;
4. Provide training in quantum computing for researchers who are expert in computational science but lack quantum computing knowledge;
5. Support career development of early career researchers through subsidised meetings, annual awards for best presentation, and a pairing scheme to link those working in computational science with those working in quantum computing and quantum algorithms;
6. Promote cross-CCP networking to share knowledge on early applications of quantum computing, enabling the widest possible early adoption of quantum enhanced computational science;
7. Provide information on early quantum computing applications in academic research to the wider community through their website maintained for the life of the CCP. The website will advertise contact details and opportunities to join the community through meetings, training days, and signposts for collaboration.

CCP-QC does not aim to develop or curate its own body of code, rather, any code developed will belong to the CCP community for that application. Pointers to those applications, and information about what works and why will be available on the website, to guide those developing further applications.

2. Highlights for the current reporting period

Supported by CCP bridge project funding, there are two work packages running in parallel, one around lattice Boltzmann in the Computational Engineering Theme and another around Green's functions formalism for electronic structure within the Computational Materials and Molecular Science Theme.

Lattice Boltzmann: As part of our broader efforts to explore the role of emerging technologies in computational science, initial work has begun to assess the potential of quantum computing for accelerating the Lattice Boltzmann Method (LBM). During the reporting period, initial activity has focused on laying a strong foundation for this new research direction. This has included an in-depth literature review spanning quantum computing fundamentals, quantum algorithms, and their relevance to fluid dynamics, as well as more targeted studies on existing attempts to connect quantum computing with LBM and related numerical methods. To support this, time was spent learning the fundamentals of quantum computing and getting started with tools such as Qiskit.

Informal catchups with collaborators helped share ideas and discuss current challenges and possible directions, while participation in the Workshop on Quantum Computing for Fluids, held in Edinburgh on 27 March 2025, helped build a better understanding of ongoing research and connect with others working in the field. Although this work is still at an early stage, these initial steps have helped highlight important questions and technical challenges and have prepared the ground for more focused investigations over the next year—particularly into how quantum computing might speed up complex flow simulations.

Electronic Structure: During this period, the CCP-QC research group worked on possible quantum algorithms for calculating Green's functions. The weekly journal club meetings have been facilitating knowledge exchange between quantum computing and materials science experts. Discussions with experimentalists running cold atom platforms that could natively encode fermions are ongoing, to determine how their hardware could measure quantities of interest to the computationalists. Quantum methods which could speed up and improve the matrix pre-conditioning step in CASTEP are under development. The QCi3 Hub (Quantum Computing via Integrated and Interconnected Implementations) has a working group on quantum algorithms for chemistry and materials, which is being linked up with the CCP-QC working group. A Royal Society Discussion Meeting was held in London 6th and 7th October <https://royalsociety.org/science-events-and-lectures/2025/10/quantum-computing/> Quantum computing in materials and molecular sciences, organised by Viv Kendon, John Buckeridge, Bruno Camino, Alin Elena, and Richard Catlow. With about 100 attendees and lively discussions it was a very successful event.

3. Overview of work relating to accelerated computing

CCP-QC is all about how quantum computing might provide future accelerators for HPC.

4. Current plans, developments, or specific applications of AI

Currently not applicable to CCP-QC. Note that the QCi3 Hub also has a quantum machine learning working group, and this may produce relevant outputs for the computational science and engineering communities.

5. Up to 5 publications that create an impact story for your community from the reporting period

1. Comprehensive review article:

Quantum algorithms for scientific computing R Au-Yeung, B Camino, O Rathore and V Kendon 2024 Rep. Prog. Phys. 87 116001 <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6633/ad85f0>

2. Ongoing work on benchmarking and standards for quantum computing led by NPL and the NQCC has created a comprehensive review and repository of code:

A Review and Collection of Metrics and Benchmarks for Quantum Computers: definitions, methodologies and software, Lall et al, <https://arxiv.org/abs/2502.06717>

6. Workshops and new opportunities*

A project entitled “Tackling the Many-Body Problem in Condensed Matter with Quantum Computing” was sent to CECAM and Psi-K. The stated date is 1-3 July 2026 or 1-3 September 2026. The workshop aims to bring together experts in many-body perturbation theory methods for classical computers and many-body methods for quantum computers.

The workshop project evaluations and the availability of funds from CECAM will be provided in December 2025.

7. Issues and problems*

None

New Communities' Report

CCP-volumeEM for the Period 01/01/2025 to 24/10/2025

Martin Jones, Chair of CCP-volumeEM

1. Background

The scope of CCP-volumeEM is to formalise a community of researchers and software engineers working in computational aspects of volume electron microscopy (vEM), which is an umbrella term for a group of EM techniques that are used to image biological material through continuous depths of at least one micrometre, at nanometre resolution. Although successful community initiatives such as volumeem.org already exist, they primarily deal with the imaging and sample preparation aspects of the field. As a result of various community surveys in this and related domains, it has become clear that the computational aspects of data storage, handling, and analysis have become the major bottleneck in many vEM workflows.

Our initial activities for the community are split into three work packages:

- **WP1: Community building** - expanding upon previous initiatives by identifying the relevant stakeholders across imaging and computational communities. We are planning two community events, the first in November 2025 for consultation on the draft roadmap, the second in Autumn/Winter 2026 to further develop the roadmap, establishing a 5-year vision. Several community hackathons and training courses will also be held over the course of the grant.
- **WP2: Research Software and Data Management** - establishing a set of best-practice guidelines, resources and exemplar projects to demonstrate scalable and flexible vEM data handling and analysis principles. This will include the integration of cutting-edge technologies such as next generation file formats (NGFF) and AI, and the promotion of FAIR data principles throughout. Ensuring these outputs are accessible to non-computational end-users will be a central focus.
- **WP3: Training and Skills** - establish a community of practice centred around key open-source analysis platforms such as Fiji and Napari, as well as the vEM specific

tools that are deployed via these platforms. Lowering the technical barriers to deploying modern workflows for both training and active research is key to this goal.

2. Highlights for the current reporting period

In WP1, much of the work so far has revolved around understanding the existing communities in the broader vEM field, and providing mechanisms for stakeholders to participate, whether they are from the end-user or developer end of the spectrum. In order to understand the current landscape of data and analysis in volume EM, a community survey ran from May to September 2025, with 62 respondents in total. This was shared via several channels, such as BioimagingUK, volumeem.org, and the EM of Cells Tissues and Organisms Slack workspace. In addition, CCP-volumeEM accounts were established on BlueSky and LinkedIn, alongside a Listserv mailing list.

To build upon the feedback from the community, a hybrid meeting will be held on 3rd November at the Francis Crick Institute in London. There are over 100 registered attendees with around 60 of those attending in person. This event aims to discuss the current landscape in volume EM data analysis and to illustrate success stories of other CCPs, leading to discussions and breakout groups to further develop the draft roadmap currently under consideration.

In WP2, efforts have focused on two main areas. Firstly, the building and testing of a range of containerised software environments across a range of commonly used bioimage analysis tools, such as Fiji, imod, MIB and napari/python. This has been led by the RSE based at the Rosalind Franklin Institute, with testing by experts in the field, helping to iteratively debug and stress-test each system, both via the STFC DAaaS VM platform, and as standalone containers for deployment elsewhere. The second focus, led by the Crick's RSE, has been to build out an exemplar workflow for generalised reconstruction of volumetric EM data, including stitching of XY tiles in 2D and registration of stitched 2D slices into a 3D stack. Existing workflows in this area are very fragmented, with different software being employed for different steps, each with its own limitations. By employing the latest technologies like next generation file formats (NGFF) and a flexible modular approach extending powerful python packages, the exemplar workflow is intended to provide a template of best-practice in building similar workflows that require scalable and efficient processing of vEM datasets. A further consideration has been the environmental impact of vEM analysis workflows, and a team member attended STFC's *Energy Efficient Computing Workshop* in September and reported back to the team with a view to implementing the best practice discussed there.

A primary goal of the containers developed in WP2 is to provide consistent and reliable computational environments for training courses, since frequently encountered challenges when delivering such courses are the accessibility of appropriate resources, such as GPUs, and the installation of complex software ecosystems on heterogeneous personal devices. As part of WP3, online and in-person training courses were delivered using these containers on the DAaaS system

in September, allowing us to better understand the broader requirements necessary for course attendees to get the most from these events.

3. Overview of work relating to accelerated computing

GPU acceleration is used in workflows employing deep learning methods such as convolutional neural networks and vision transformer models for processing steps like image segmentation. Widespread usage of these best-in-class methods is still limited due to the current challenges in accessibility of these tools to the broader biology research community. This is caused by variable access to appropriate heterogeneous computing resources, limited development of user-friendly interfaces to the tools, and lack of training resources. The CCP-volumeEM activities are all targeted towards removing these hurdles.

4. Current plans, developments, or specific applications of AI

Many promising AI methods have been developed by the vEM community, for example the “empanada” plugin for the napari package in python, as well as by the broader AI industry, such as Meta.AI’s Segment Anything Model (SAM). Frequently, the bottleneck is not necessarily the *availability* of AI methods, but rather the *accessibility*, from the use of pre-trained models for inference, through the fine-tuning of pre-trained and foundation models, all the way to designing and training new models from scratch. Bioimaging experiments are typically characterised by very specific sample preparation and imaging conditions that often exceed the generalisation capabilities of pre-trained models, requiring extensive fine-tuning. To assist in the further establishment of the *empanada* plugin as a user-friendly interface for accessing and fine-tuning well generalised models across a range of segmentation targets, the CCP is supporting the developers to ensure the tool is able to leverage the latest advances in the python and napari ecosystems, led by the RSE at CoSeC.

5. Up to 5 research outputs that create an impact story for your community from the reporting period

One of the most impactful developments in vEM image analysis recently has been the empanada napari plugin for organelle segmentation (<https://empanada.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>). This was developed at NIH in the US, utilising a Panoptic DeepLab architecture with extensive semi-supervised pre-training on diverse datasets, before a round of supervised training on manually generated ground truth data. Developments this year have seen additional new models released, now covering segmentation of mitochondria, nuclei and lipid droplets, with improved proofreading and fine-tuning capabilities. The generalised nature of these models has seen them established as the preferred choice in many applications. CCP-volumeEM has recently embarked upon an exercise to update the package to work with more modern versions of python and scientific libraries.

An increasingly common class of workflow using vEM methods is correlative and multimodal imaging, for example correlative light and electron microscopy (CLEM). The additional complexity of handling and aligning datasets of very different resolution and field of view has historically required entirely manual alignment. CLEM-Reg

(<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-025-02794-0>) automates this process, leveraging AI based segmentation to generate modality agnostic point clouds, which can be aligned using probabilistic methods. The use of NGFF in managing multimodal imaging projects avoids the necessity of duplicating and re-casting datasets into a common pixel space, instead allowing them to be related by relative spatial transformations stored as metadata. For this task, the MoBIE plugin in Fiji was extensively used in “A nanopathology pipeline for clinical research across scales using human tissue” (<https://doi.org/10.1101/2025.08.29.25334660>), with several terabytes of x-ray, light and vEM data being uploaded to the BioImage Archive repository as part of the publication.

6. Workshops and new opportunities*

Towards a collaborative computational community for volume EM, 3rd November, Francis Crick Institute, London

NGFF Hackathon: A two-day hackathon focussed on bridging the gap between the amazing potential of OME-NGFF for the volume EM community, and the current reality through work on tools, training, tutorials, and example workflows. Date TBC, Jan 2026

7. Issues and problems*

A major consideration for the CCP is to identify the highest impact activities to undertake. Due to the nature of the historic evolution of the field, many different tools are employed for the same tasks, making it difficult to determine which tools would be most beneficial to support directly. Ensuring developer effort is directed towards the areas of highest community benefit will need to be guided by the broader community of end-users and developers.

CCC-ParaSolS for the Period 05/06/2025 to 05/11/2025

Dr Kevin Hanley, Chair of CCC-ParaSolS

1. Background

CCC-ParaSolS (ccc-parasols.ed.ac.uk) is a community open to all UK-based scientists and engineers from academia and industry with a common interest in simulating particulate solids (granular materials) for a variety of applications. These granular materials include natural soil deposits, pharmaceutical powders, food ingredients (e.g., salt, flour, agricultural grains), and aggregates and cement used in construction. The most popular particle-scale simulation method is the Discrete Element Method (DEM), although there are many others. Three open-source DEM codes have been selected for consideration in CCC-ParaSolS: LAMMPS, MercuryDPM and YADE.

Currently, developments of particulate simulation methods happen in discipline silos, inhibiting full exploitation of methodological advancements. CCC-ParaSolS aims to address this issue by creating an overarching, multi-disciplinary community which embeds diversity and inclusiveness in its composition, governance, and activities. CCC-ParaSolS is promoting the use of open-source software for granular simulations, delivering bespoke training on DEM code and HPC usage, hosting physical network

events at different UK locations, undertaking a high-priority code development project based on community needs analyses, and creating a five-year vision for the community. Through these activities and more, CCC-ParaSolS will establish a strong foundation for a long-term Collaborative Computational Project in particulate solids simulations.

2. Highlights for the current reporting period

Networking and training opportunities: Since the last CoSeC Community Forum in Sheffield, CCC-ParaSolS held its second Network Event in a hybrid manner at the Cosener's House, Abingdon, Oxfordshire from 13–15 October (ccc-parasols.ed.ac.uk/events/past/network-event-2/). The first day of this three-day event included:

- Group discussions to shape our collective five-year vision for the community;
- Convergence towards one single code development project to focus on in year 2;
- A summary of progress made in developing code benchmarking cases;
- A practical introduction to the CCC-ParaSolS online discussion forum;
- 'Flash' research presentations from volunteers.

Days 2 and 3 consisted of [training delivered by experts from EPCC](#) on the use of HPC with ARCHER2 as an exemplar, and running a DEM simulation on ARCHER2 with LAMMPS (& the Granular package). This Network Event was very successful, attracting ~25 in-person attendees and 5–10 online attendees each day.

In-person attendees at Network Event 2 (Oxfordshire, 13–15 October)

Community growth: CCC-ParaSolS has expanded to almost 90 full members and >150 [followers on LinkedIn](#). Several promotional activities to grow the community further have either taken place or are scheduled:

- The CCC-ParaSolS leads [are presenting a NAFEMS webinar](#) on 28 October on “Discrete Element Modelling of Particulate Solids Processes in Industry”.
- The CCC-ParaSolS leads have proposed a mini-symposium (“Discrete element method simulations: Research advances and the CCC-ParaSolS community”) at the [2026 Annual Conference](#) of the [UK Association for Computational Mechanics](#).
- Presentations about CCC-ParaSolS are planned at the 22nd UK Travelling Workshop in GeoMechanics: from Micro to Macro (GM3) in December 2025 and the [2026 NAFEMS UK Conference](#).

Online discussion forum: To facilitate community engagement with Network Events, a discussion forum has been created on Discourse: [parasols.discourse.group](#) This was launched in early October.

Future code development: A form to gather community suggestions for code development projects to focus on in year 2 was circulated in August (supported by an online webinar and Q&A by the CCC-ParaSolS leads). These suggestions were reviewed by the Management Committee on 2 September. For several reasons, adding GPU capabilities to MercuryDPM was the suggestion favoured by the Management Committee. This proposal was presented at the second Network Event and received majority agreement from attendees after an open discussion.

3. Overview of work relating to accelerated computing

In year 2 of CCC-ParaSolS, the CoSeC developer time will be spent making progress on adding GPU capabilities to MercuryDPM. This follows a transparent and comprehensive process (see above) in which we identified this as the development to prioritise as the one of greatest benefit to the community. The early phase of this code implementation project will involve determining the best route by which to add these GPU capabilities, in consultation with the lead developer of MercuryDPM at the University of Manchester.

4. Current plans, developments, or specific applications of AI

A great deal of research is being done among the community on the use of AI to accelerate, improve or otherwise complement DEM simulations, but in a somewhat piecemeal fashion. The third Network Event will focus on the current use of AI among the DEM community and its expected uptake in the next five years. This event will tentatively take place in January, hosted by the University of Manchester. Its format has not been defined at the time of writing; it could, for instance, include invited talks, discussion workshops, debates, and/or training provision.

5. Up to 5 research outputs that create an impact story for your community from the reporting period

While community members are doing highly impactful research, it is too early to attribute this to CCC-ParaSolS. The main research output from CCC-ParaSolS is a repository of training materials and learning resources, to benefit researchers starting to use DEM or learning a new open-source code: [ccc-](#)

parasols.ed.ac.uk/resources/tutorials & [ccc-parasols.ed.ac.uk/resources/learning_materials](https://parasols.ed.ac.uk/resources/learning_materials)

6. Workshops and new opportunities*

We anticipate two hybrid Network Events between now and April 2026. Dates for both have yet to be decided:

- Network Event 3: tentatively in January at the University of Manchester, focused on AI;
- Network Event 4: tentatively in March at Queen's University Belfast as a [joint event with the ON-DEM COST Action](#).

Several fully online events will follow these in 2026.

7. Issues and problems*

Clarity about funding to enable these Collaborative Computational Community scoping projects to become full Collaborative Computational Projects after December 2026 would be welcome.

CCP-DCM for the Period 01/06/2025 to 31/10/2025

Prof. David Ham, Chair of CCP-DCM

1. Background

This is a [collaborative computational community](#) centred around the FEniCS and Firedrake finite element systems. [FEniCS](#) and [Firedrake](#) are world-leading software frameworks for the numerical solution of partial differential equations (PDEs). These numerical simulations are essential for advancing science and engineering across a very broad range of disciplines. FEniCS and Firedrake are used to develop solvers in the geosciences (ocean, atmosphere, cryosphere, geodynamics), nuclear fusion (plasma, tritium transport, breeding blankets), physiology and medicine (brain, heart), and many more besides. Our role is to support and develop the core simulation toolchain to enable current and new users to continue to push the limits of the possible in simulation scale, and to support and grow the user and developer community through a rich range of support mechanisms including tutorials, workshops, hackathons, web fora and chat channels, written and video documentation, on-site visits and mentoring relationships.

2. Highlights for the current reporting period

The summer period included two significant user and developer workshops, the FEniCS conference in Groningen and the Firedrake workshop in Leeds. These are important community building workshops which enable members of the community from the most experienced to the very newest to exchange ideas and provide assistance.

On the technical front, there has been significant work to improve the high-level programming interface, UFL, which is common to Firedrake and FEniCS. Improvements include simplification of both the interface and implementation, thereby improving usability and reducing the level of technical debt in the package. Substantive

functionality improvements merged over this period have included improvements to support for coupled simulations (enabling users to simulate more complete physical systems) and improved interfaces to interpolation, which is essential to the incorporation of real data into simulations.

We have continued to build our community by conducting a scoping meeting including academic, government and industry representatives. This will feed into the interim and final reports for this phase of the CCP. In order to maximise community engagement, we have prepared and will shortly release a community survey. This will inform our priorities in both technical developments and the community support mechanisms that we prioritise in the coming years.

Conferences, meetings, hackathons:

- CCP Scoping meeting – 3 June 2025
- FEniCS Conference in Groningen, Netherlands – 18-20 June 2025
- Firedrake '25 workshop, Leeds – 15-17 September 2025

Tutorials:

- FEniCS tutorial at IBSim-4i (Chris Richardson) 21 Oct 2025
- Firedrake adjoint tutorial, Leeds 16 September 2025

3. Overview of work relating to accelerated computing

FEniCS has an ongoing programme of GPU related work. To increase arithmetic intensity, we have developed a p-multigrid solver for hexahedral meshes. Using EuroHPC resources at LUMI, Finland, we wrote a new matrix-free FEniCS-based code for the AMD MI250x GPU using HIP/CUDA. With few modifications, the same code runs on NVIDIA devices, and we benchmarked the performance against libCEED, a US-based exascale project. On the MI250x, we can outperform libCEED on hexahedral meshes. We have collected performance data on NVIDIA A100, GH200, AMD MI300x, and workstation GPUs. Further work on tetrahedral meshes is underway and shows promising results.

We are increasing the number of external GPU libraries which we can interface to, either via PETSc, or directly to NVIDIA and AMD libraries, such as cudss, amgX, and rocalution. Details of the p-multigrid solver are published as: “An efficient multigrid solver for finite element methods on multi-GPU systems” - Chris N. Richardson*, Igor A. Baratta, Joseph P. Dean, William Adrian Jackson, Garth N. Wells. Proceedings of the Third EuroHPC User Days, 21 Sept 2025, vol 267, p82-91.

Firedrake is collaborating with NVIDIA to prototype new code generation pathways for GPU based on suitable MLIR dialects. These should allow higher level algorithmic information to be passed to vendor compiler tools than is the case when generating code in low-level languages such as CUDA C, OpenCL or HIP. Preliminary investigations conducted in summer 2025 have identified potential MLIR dialects, and we are currently seeking funding to take this work further.

4. Current plans, developments, or specific applications of AI

The high-level code-generation approach adopted in Firedrake and FEniCS produces an execution model akin to the differentiable programming models that are universal in the neural network community. Using Firedrake (similar capabilities are in development for FEniCS), users can automatically differentiate their simulation code. This enables the solution of optimisation problems to learn parameters and parameterisations, optimal topologies and other configuration learning challenges. That is to say, Firedrake is an AI tool for simulation science. For example, the Microsoft press release cited below describes it in those terms. Employing the same differentiable programming execution model as tools such as PyTorch and Jax also enables hybrid approaches, in which a differential equation models those parts of the system for which we have physical laws, and a neural network is used for those parts for which we do not. Firedrake is already in use for these sorts of combined PDE/neural network problem, for example in the following preprints.

- Rowbottom, J., Maierhofer, G., Deveney, T., Müller, E., Paganini, A., Schratz, K., Lio, P., Schönlieb, C.-B., & Budd, C. (Accepted/In press). G-Adaptivity: optimised graph-based mesh relocation for finite element methods. Paper presented at 42nd International Conference on Machine Learning, Vancouver. <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2407.04516>
- Farsi, A., Bouziani, N., & Ham, D. A. (2025). Missing Physics Discovery through Fully Differentiable Finite Element-Based Machine Learning. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2507.15787>

Inverse learning problems constitute a large portion of Firedrake's applications, and we are currently working on both performance and capability enhancements, particularly for complex coupled simulations.

5. Up to 5 research outputs that create an impact story for your community from the reporting period

Topology Optimisation for High Performance Chip Cooling

Microsoft released news of a breakthrough in the design of liquid cooling channels for microchips: <https://news.microsoft.com/source/features/innovation/microfluidics-liquid-cooling-ai-chips/> . This work is being conducted by tech startup Corintis using Firedrake to learn optimised channel topologies using inverse PDE simulation.

Software Releases

Firedrake released version 2025.10.0, marking the second six-monthly regular release of the package. This new release schedule is critical to providing stability for downstream packages, such as the Gusto atmospheric modelling toolkit used at the Met Office, and to direct users of Firedrake such as the UK Atomic Energy Agency.

FEniCS released version 0.10.0 containing a large number of improvements over the 12 months since 0.9.0. Key improvements include enhanced nonlinear solver support,

IO improvements and documentation improvements in support of the user community.

6. Workshops and new opportunities*

- Firedrake '26 & PETSc '26 1-5 June 2026: Colocation of the annual Firedrake and PETSc user and developer meetings.
https://www.firedrakeproject.org/firedrake_26.html
- FEniCS Conference 17-19 June, 2026, Paris: annual conference with student talks and tutorial session.
- OSSFE 10-12 March 2026, Munich: invited FEniCS tutorial at nuclear fusion software conference.
- FEniCS online tutorial/conference (in planning, joint with Simula, Norway) - Spring 2026.

7. Issues and problems*

Continuity of funding for Firedrake support may be an issue in 2026 as there will be a gap between the RSE support funded by the initial CCP project and the potential further support in a full CCP. We are currently bidding for funds to bridge this gap.

CCP-TEPP for the Period 05/06/2025 to 28/10/2025

Dr Ed Bennett, CCP-TEPP project lead

Dr Ben Morgan, CCP-TEPP project co-lead

1. Background

CCP-TEPP is the Collaborative Computational Project in Theoretical and Experimental Particle Physics. This covers a diverse community, including but not limited to lattice quantum field theorists, members of the LHC experimental collaborations, and phenomenologists sitting at the interface between these groups. Computational approaches span from large high-performance computing-based Monte Carlo approaches to computations in lattice quantum chromodynamics and beyond the Standard Model physics, to high-throughput grid computing approaches to the processing of collider data.

2. Highlights for the current reporting period

The main activity in this period has been [a knowledge exchange event held at the Daresbury Laboratory in September 2025](#). 36 participants (including 13 invited speakers) presented on and discussed topics where there are common challenges across the field, as identified from our road mapping workshops earlier in the year. Topics discussed included computational infrastructure, automation and reproducibility of data analysis, accelerators and performance portability, software maintainability and code quality, applications of quantum computing, and applications of machine learning technologies.

Work on the final version of the roadmap arising from the workshops earlier in the year is ongoing; we anticipate a public draft in the coming weeks.

3. Overview of work relating to accelerated computing

As a New Community, technical effort funded by CCP-TEPP will commence in 2026. Accelerated computing is already essential for many workloads in particle physics, and enabling more groups and projects to take advantage of these resources is anticipated to be a significant portion of the technical work.

4. Current plans, developments, or specific applications of AI

As a New Community, technical effort funded by CCP-TEPP will commence in 2026. The current status of AI within particle physics was summarised at the September meeting by one of the authors of the document [Enabling AI for High Energy Physics Experiment and Theory](#).

5. Up to 5 research outputs that create an impact story for your community from the reporting period

The review [The anomalous magnetic moment of the muon in the Standard Model: an update \[Phys.Rept. 1143 \(2025\) 1-158\]](#) highlights that state-of-the-art lattice quantum field theory calculations are able to provide world-leading estimates for the hadronic vacuum polarisation contribution to the anomalous magnetic moment of the muon, resolving long-standing tensions between theory and experiment.

As mentioned above, the document [Enabling AI for High Energy Physics Experiment and Theory](#) outlines the current status and future directions of machine-learning-informed approaches in particle physics.

A community meeting [AdePT and Celeritas for Detector Simulation on GPUs](#) reported on progress in development of codes for running the critically important and computationally intensive detector simulation component of the experimental workflow. This led to a hackathon integrating these codes into the ATLAS experiment's data processing framework and the first profiling and validation runs on the LHC GPU Grid clusters.

In the area of simulation for event generation, a [LHC Monte Carlo Working Group](#) workshop was held bringing together developers and users of these codes.

Highlights were sessions on [Code Acceleration](#) and [Sustainability of the MC Toolchain](#) showing the importance the community attaches to both increasing the performance of their codes and keeping them maintained and supported over the long term.

6. Workshops and new opportunities*

We are working with CoSeC to host a Summer School on computational techniques for particle physics in Summer 2026. The dates and exact content of this event are yet to be finalised.

We are in the early stages of planning additional targeted events for 2026 based on the challenges identified in our road mapping. This is likely to include a docathon retreat, in addition to focused intra-community knowledge exchange events.

7. Issues and problems*

Uncertainty and delays around STFC Consolidated Grants are causing difficulties across the field. The end of funding for SWIFT-HEP is creating a cliff edge in certain parts of the community.

CCP-UKNR for the Period 01/05/2025 to 01/11/2025

Prof. Eugene Lim, Chair of CCP-UKN

1. Background

No change to previous.

2. Highlights for the current reporting period

- a) The major highlight of this period is the very successful **Numerical Relativity 2025 : Towards the Next Generation** (<https://sites.google.com/view/nrgregynog/>) workshop held from **17-19th June, 2025** at the historical Gregynog Hall venue (which is the site of the first ever numerical relativity workshop held in 1980). This workshop brought together the members of the CCP-UKNR community, CoSeC and international stake holders. In particular, the latter included Katherine Riley, who is the Director of Science for the US Argonne National Lab (which operates the first exascale machines Aurora and Frontier), and Mark Wilkinson who is the Director of DiRAC. The goal of the workshop was threefold:
 - **Science** : Discuss the state of the art of numerical relativity, and the code development and strategies to confront the increasingly challenging precision requirements dictated by upcoming experiments in particular the international LISA space-based mission in which the UK is a major partner.
 - **Strategic Planning** : Understand the present and future digital landscape for the next 5-10 years, and the challenges it will bring to numerical relativity.
 - **Community Building** : Discuss and formulate actions that will strengthen the foundations of a good community.

For further details, a published report on this workshop is available on our website (<https://www.uknumericalrelativity.org/ccp-development>).

- b) **MHDuet**, a GPU-enabled magnetohydro-GR code led by **Dr Miguel Bezares**, lecturer at Nottingham University, has been released (<https://arxiv.org/abs/2510.13965> <http://mhduet.liu.edu/>), marking a major milestone in the GPU-readiness of CCP-UKNR.
- c) **Dr Miquel Miravet Tenes**, who is a postdoctoral researcher at Southampton University is appointed as a **CoSeC Fellow**. As part of his remit, he will be developing a Mentorship programme for the CCP-UKNR community and organising inter-community journal clubs especially for early career scientists.
- d) **Dr Katy Clough**, senior lecturer at QMUL and Rutherford Fellow, and a Co-I for the CCP-UKNR, was awarded a highly prestigious **Simons Foundation Collaboration Grant** as a PI. The grant aims to characterise non linearities around black holes in the strong, dynamical regime of gravitational theories, with numerical relativity tools playing a key role in their study.

3. Overview of work relating to accelerated computing

Our community is fully engaged in the process of transitioning into a new digital infrastructure landscape where we expect most (if not all) future UK compute is GPU-based.

- a) As mentioned above, the GPU-enabled version of **MHDuet** led by **Dr Miguel Bezares** with assistance from **Dr Miren Radia**, has been released in October 2025. MHDuet is a CUDA-enabled MHD-GR code built on AMReX and SAMRAI. The code is continually being improved and optimised.
- b) The GRTL Code Collaboration's successor to their groundbreaking **GRChombo** code, **GRTeclyn**, is expected to be released by December. GRTeclyn, also built on AMReX, is a fully GPU-platform independent numerical relativity code, compatible with the three major GPU

protocols (AMD-Hip, CUDA and SYCL) in addition the standard CPU infrastructures.

- c) ExaGRyPE, a multi-purpose numerical relativity code developed in Durham by **Prof Baojiu Li**, **Prof Tobias Weinzierl** and **Dr Han Zhang**, has been connected to the modular LLVM stack, allowing it to run natively on all GPU platforms with LLVM-based compilers, allowing it to easily exceed 2-3 times speed up – see figure below. Furthermore, the development of this code has led to several cross-cutting contributions, in particular the development team has contributed new tasking features to the Intel Thread Building Blocks, and new extensions to the C++ language which are application generic.

a.

- d) We are also undertaking a community wide **benchmarking exercise**, funded by the CCP, and led by Technical Lead **Dr Miren Radia**, with support from PI **Prof Eugene Lim**, and Co-Is **Prof Mark Hannam** and **Dr Katy Clough**, to take a “screenshot” of the present CPU and GPU performance of the present and prospective NR codes : the UK-led GRTEclyn and GRChombo, MHDuet, EXAGryPE, and the international codes ETK/Carpet, ETK/CarpetX, and BAM. We have obtained a discretionary allocation from DiRAC of **500000 CPU/hrs and 4500 GPU Node/hrs (in COSMA8 and Tursa)** to undertake this project. The expected completion date is March 2026. This will be fed back into the community to make an informed decision about code choices and will allow us to assess the community’s readiness for the next generation compute.

4. Current plans, developments, or specific applications of AI

- a) PI **Prof Eugene Lim** is collaborating with Dr Boxuan Ge from the CAS to develop a CNN-based algorithm to generate gravitational waves data based on trained input results from simulation data. We are also looking at how one might use

CNN algorithms to “upscale” initial conditions data as a proof of concept to use neural networks to solve elliptic equations.

- b) The **METHOD** code group (led by **Prof Ian Hawke**) is developing a machine learning strategy to implement turbulence closure in sub grid models for relativistic magnetized turbulence. This is based on their published paper *Phys.Rev.D* 110 (2024) 12, 123040.
 - c) Both the GRTEclyn and the ExaGRyPE developers are exploring the use of LLM to self-generate documentation for their respective codes.
5. Up to 5 research outputs that create an impact story for your community from the reporting period
- a) In *Lecture Notes in Computer Science Advancing OpenMP for Future Accelerators*, p.210-224, **Prof Tobias Weinzierl** using ExaGRyPE documented and published a conditional flaw in the OpenMP Task scheduling and proposed that more prescriptive statements would enforce correct OpenMP behaviour during runtime.
 - b) Work from the CCP-UKNR community was highlighted in major public event *New Scientist Live!* (held annually in the EXCEL centre, with over 26000 attendees in 2025), by **Dr Katy Clough**.

- a) CCP-UKNR scientists were involved in two significant papers from the LIGO-Virgo-KAGRA Collaboration. Firstly, Co-I **Prof Mark Hannam** was the lead editor of a major paper (<https://arxiv.org/abs/2507.08219>) on the most massive binary black hole merger detected thus far. This work generated significant media coverage in which Prof Hannam was quoted, including in *The Guardian*, *CNN*, and *Nature*. Many members of the CCP-UKNR community also worked on this paper. Secondly, CCP-UKNR scientists, including Co-Is

Dr **Geraint Pratten** and Dr **Patricia Schmidt** were heavily involved in using numerical relativity to test Hawking’s famous Area Theorem in another key paper (<https://arxiv.org/abs/2509.08054>) which was also broadly covered by the media.

6. Workshops and new opportunities*

- a) CCP-UKNR Annual Meeting (Birmingham, 15-16 Dec 2025)
- b) CCP-UKNR Annual “Future of Numerical Relativity Workshop”, summer 2026.
- c) We are looking to share experiences with CCPs on using single-precision processors in high precision HPC.

7. Issues and problems*

None.

CCP-AHC for the Period 04/06/2025 to 24/10/2025

Dr Eamonn Bell, Chair of CCP-AHC

1. Background

CCP-AHC (www.ccpahc.ac.uk) focuses on DRI and software that support computationally intensive research and innovation in the arts, humanities, and culture (AHC) fields. This research is typically funded by in the UK by UKRI’s Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC). Our scope includes any code, pipelines, or workflows developed by the community that is running or has the potential to run on UK-funded HPC and advanced computing resource, including those targeting GPUs and other novel accelerators. Earlier efforts to gather community requirements targeting AHRC-facing researchers offer some insights into HPC and cloud computing usage to date, where 38% of survey respondents used or were moving to “HPC/Cloud” in 2021. Our aim is to increase this proportion by curating a portfolio of codes, pipelines, and workflows that represent community needs and ambitions for computationally intensive AHC research. We also recognise the vital role of datasets in driving adoption.

Given the widespread interest in and adoption of AI methods within the field, we emphasise projects have the potential to drive engagement with and widen access to the DRI that supports these methods. This includes the FAIR data infrastructures within the AHRC’s portfolio of DRI projects, the Infrastructure for Digital Arts and Humanities (iDAH), the national skills hubs, and ongoing Network+ activities in federated and sustainable computing.

We look to find projects with the potential for development through engagement with RSE and computational science resource within CCP-AHC and CoSeC during the scoping project and over the longer-term future of this project and related initiatives. We do this through a combination of responsive open calls for research software submissions, desk research, and community engagement exercises.

2. Highlights for the current reporting period

CCP-AHC has published an open draft of the CCP-AHC Roadmap (<https://zenodo.org/records/17099176>), which is available on Zenodo. This is based on the outcomes of the CCP-AHC Town Hall 2025 and will form the basis for consultation at forthcoming community engagement events and the mid-term report to CoSeC. We have currently received 21 projects in response to an open call for codes, pipelines, and workflows (<https://www.ccpahc.ac.uk/activities/codes-eoi/>). We supported a community member with a full submission to the Software Sustainability Institute (SSI) Research Software Maintenance Fund.

We presented a poster detailing the initiative at PASC'25 (see 5. below) and received feedback from European projects, including colleagues at the Dutch national social science infrastructure ODISSEI, which led to a follow-up meeting with colleagues at SURF. We also took part at the DRI Congress 2025 (Leeds, 22-23 October 2025), as an invited project within the AHRC-organised panel “From Foundations to Frontiers: Connecting Infrastructures in the Digital Arts and Humanities”. Since the last reporting period, we held an additional sixteen online stakeholder meetings. These include meetings with representatives of major AHRC investments including RICHeS and CoSTAR, key staff at other DRI investments (e.g. STFC’s IRIS, DiRAC), as well as prospective community members (i.e. codes owners and maintainers).

We have grown the JISCMail mailing lists for CCP-AHC-ANNOUNCE (announcements and news) and CCP-AHC-DISCUSS (community discussion) to 119 and 79 subscribers (up from 70 and 40, respectively). We have posted regular newsletter-style mailings summarising information from allied DRI projects for our members. Monthly online CCP-AHC Community Forums began in August 2025, with an average attendance of ten per meeting. Guest presentations were held on Galaxy for Digital Humanities (Daniela Schneider, Galaxy Europe/University of Freiburg) and the PDSI Data Revival service (Jeremy Frey and Sam Munday, Data Revival). On 24 October 2025, the SSI’s blog featured a write-up of the CCP-AHC Town Hall 2025 by an attendee and SSI Fellow, Dr Katherine McDonough (<https://www.software.ac.uk/blog/high-performance-computing-and-arts-and-humanities-research-uk>).

A pilot training workshop on AI tools for working with scanned documents was delivered at University of Luxembourg, Centre for Contemporary and Digital History (C2DH) on 14 October 2025, (<https://github.com/ccpahc/meta/wiki/Tools-for-working-with-scans-of-PDFs-hosted-on-Internet-Archive>). The workshop showed how FAIR image publication standards (IIIF) and open-source tools (Voxel51’s fiftyone) can be used together to run computationally intensive AI workflows using cultural heritage datasets without code.

Our project site (www.ccpahc.ac.uk) has 150 seven-day active users at the time of writing. CCP-AHC has developed a new resource that indexes the public-facing documentation pages for UK HPC sites (<https://www.ccpahc.ac.uk/resources/sites/>). A prototype full-text search appliance is integrated into the page, which allows users to search over the documentation contents for many sites. This has been developed in

response to a need within CCP-AHC to help community members find the resources associated with their home institution and/or regional consortium.

We believe this project has relevance to other communities: to help them understand the hardware and software landscape across multiple sites, to better understand trends and best-practices in user documentation, and to lower the barrier to accessing state- and HEI-funded compute. Pull requests to ensure complete coverage are welcome (<https://github.com/ccpahc/ccpahc.github.io/edit/main/docs/data/hpc-sites.yaml>).

3. Overview of work relating to accelerated computing

Work to prioritise projects that stand to benefit from hardware acceleration continues. The strong interest in AI from our community underscores the importance of working within the accelerated compute landscape. In addition to advocating for benchmarking and support across a variety of GPU manufacturers within the community, we are also scoping community interest in application-specific accelerators (e.g. Cerebras) as well as the resource and training needed to support their adoption. CCP-AHC enjoys a coinvestigator team with members in the SHAREing national dRTP skills hub for accelerated compute (Bell) and the UKRI Living Benchmarks project (Thiyagalingam). These leverage the CCP to provide greater reach for and understanding of AHC research software within the wider UK DRI ecosystem.

4. Current plans, developments, or specific applications of AI

Work to prioritise projects in the application of AI to arts, humanities, and cultural datasets continues. Our community has emphasized the importance of several tasks to accelerating their research. These include automatic speech recognition, optical character recognition, handwritten text recognition, document layout analysis, visual question answering, and zero-shot text and image classification.

Each of these tasks are well known in applied computer science, and recent developments in AI methods have seen dramatic improvements in task performance compared to classical approaches. We plan to develop infrastructures that make efficient batch inference of these GPU-intensive models more widely available to researchers on a pilot basis, for a subset of these tasks.

5. Up to 5 research outputs that create an impact story for your community from the reporting period

E. Bell and K. Rodriguez Echavarria, “Fostering the Wider Adoption of High-Performance Computing by UK-Based Arts and Humanities Researchers via National Training and Community-Building Initiatives,” presented at the PASC’25 Conf., Brugg-Windisch, Switzerland, Jun. 16–18, 2025.

6. Workshops and new opportunities*

CCP-AHC will hold four regional engagement events in the coming months. The following events are confirmed:

- CCP-AHC Engagement Event (Cardiff) on Wednesday, 29th October 2025, 12.30pm to 3.30pm at Wales Millennium Centre, Cardiff
- CCP-AHC Engagement Event (Edinburgh) on Thursday, 6th November 2025, 1pm to 5 pm at University of Edinburgh, Edinburgh
- CCP-AHC Engagement Event (London) on Friday, 14th November 2025, 12.30pm to 4pm, Central London

We can also announce a “save the date” for the CCP-AHC Town Hall 2026, which will take place on 17th September 2026 at STFC Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (Harwell, Oxfordshire). Looking forward to Summer 2026, CCP-AHC will also contribute the Digital Humanities & Research Software Engineering Summer School 2026 (location and date TBC).

We invite members of all other communities and the CoSeC programme office to these events to explore opportunities for cross- community working and to share their experiences.

7. Issues and problems*

We need a clearer understanding of the technical resource that is available within STFC during the second year of the project. This includes details about lead time, availability/capacity constraints, and specific capabilities. CCP-AHC does not benefit from co-investigator relationships with STFC prior to the scoping project start date, which would otherwise speed this process.

Similarly, we have found a lack of “headroom” within AHRC-funded projects which might otherwise be used to co-develop CCP-AHC workshops and activities. The average software-producing AHRC grant is significantly smaller than the comparable average from other councils, and it is often the case that software outputs that have been sent to CCP-AHC are currently unfunded by active projects. Some community members even struggle to engage with requirements elicitation exercises on an unfunded basis.

**Computational Science Centre
for Research Communities**

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